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A user friendly catalogue of state-of-the-art soil health practices

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This is a catalogue of agricultural practices that have the potential of improving soil health. This is phrased more elaborately than the title of this catalogue, because application of the described practices will not automatically improve soil health. Whether or not they will do so, depends on a variety of factors which are addressed in the practice sheets.

The main purpose of this catalogue is providing inspiration for the living labs which are part of the HORIZON EU SOILCRATES project activities. These living labs will be implementing experiments with innovative soil improvement practices and this catalogue can help decide on what experiments would be particularly useful to implement as living lab participants. Furthermore, this catalogue will later also play a role in the dissemination of best practices to increase soil literacy.

The information is meant to provide a rather elaborate summary overview, and for selected practices more information can be obtained through links to further reading that are provided as well.

Descriptions are relatively short, and for this reason suggestions for further reading are included as well (chapter four). To further inspire decision-making processes in the living labs, a few 'out-of-the-box' practices are included in a more concise description as well (chapter three).

Work on the catalogues and related products will continue over the next few years as part of the mission of SOILCRATES, specifically as part of task 5.4. Related deliverables will be made available through the SOILCRATES website (<https://soilcrates.eu/>).

1.2 Method

The development of the practice sheets involved the following collaborative process:

1. Exploration (longlist) of possible practices to include in the catalogue as T5.1 partners. These partners represent expertise on soil health for Spain, France, Italy, Ireland, and the Netherlands.
2. Selection (shortlist) of practices as T5.1 partners.
3. Development of a template for the practice sheets, which after various iterations was approved by T5.1 partners.
4. Three rounds of development of contents of the practice sheets (and related materials), which involved developing drafts based on selected literature, receiving feedback from T5.1 partners and their direct colleagues after every round.
5. Sharing first complete drafts with all partners SOILCRATES, notably those involved directly in the SOILCRATES living labs, asking for their feedback, and testing user friendliness.
6. Last round of upgrading and in-between checks with T5.1 partners to ensure agreement on the final version.

1.3 Setup

The core of this catalogue is **chapter two**, which contains two-pager descriptions of 35 agricultural practices. The legend at the beginning of the chapter (2.1) describes how the practice sheets are meant to be interpreted. Practice number six can be applied with such variety that we decided to split it up into four sub-practice descriptions.

Chapter three summarizes key soil health benefits related to the selected practices. In chapter four, a few **innovative practices** are described in less detail. These are often practices which have not been researched sufficiently, but may nevertheless inspire living labs.

Chapter five briefly refers to a background document on policies and regulations related to soil health management practices. It can be accessed on the SOILCRATES website since it is a living document and will be updated as the work of SOILCRATES progresses.

Chapter six provides an **overview of further reading material** with sources from Italy, Spain, France, Ireland, and the Netherlands. A simple overview enables a quick check regarding which sources provide further information on which practices.

Chapter seven presents the **longlist of agricultural practices that were considered** and from which a shortlist of 35 practices was selected.

Chapter eight closes with a brief conclusion.

2 The practice sheets

2.1 The legend

The following explains the indications provides in the practice sheets. Please note that the indications under 5., 6., and 11. are approximate only because of the variety of conditions that need to be considered for many of the practices.

LEGEND:

1. Name/descriptor of practice
2. Basic description of practice
3. Practical advice on application
4. Crops (for which this practice is particularly relevant)
5. Potential impact

<i>Indication</i>	<i>Meaning</i>
--	Seriously negative impact
-	Some negative impact
0	Neutral
+	Some positive impact
++	Seriously positive impact

Options for ecosystem services

Provisioning

- biomass provision

Regulating

- Climate regulation
- Water regulation
- Erosion control
- Pollution control
- Pest and disease regulation

Supporting

- Nutrient cycling
- Provision of habitat
- Biodiversity

Cultural (non-material)

- Cultural and non-material elements

6. Application considerations

- a. Suitable soil (marked which one(s) apply)
- b. Suitable climate (marked which one(s) apply)
- c. Application costs - labour (indicated what applies)

<i>Indication</i>	<i>Means</i>
●	Less work → Saves time
○	Same as standard practice
●	More work → Requires extra effort
●	Much more work → Requires significant effort

- d. Application costs - materials (indicated what applies)

<i>Indication</i>	<i>Means</i>
●	Lower costs → Saves money
○	Same as standard practice
●	More costs → Requires extra investment
●	Much more costs → Requires significant investment

e. **Difficulty/knowledge needed to apply** (indicated what applies)

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Meaning</i>
0	Nothing different than general farm practice
1	Involves limited new application knowledge and experience
2	Takes some effort to (learn how to) apply
3	Takes a significant effort to (learn how to) apply

f. **Suitable scale of application as indicated**

g. **Information on relevant legislation and regulations.**

Scan the QR-code which leads to draft document with information on relevant policies and regulations for France, Ireland, Italy, Spain, and the Netherlands.

8. **Extent to which well-researched**

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Meaning</i>
1	Limited: with some effort a few sources can be found
2	Average: general descriptions can be found
3	More than average: one of the focus areas of soil-related research
4	Significant: a lot of research has been done – many sources available

9. **Further considerations**

10. **Research**

11. **Potential soil health benefit (marked are the ones that apply)**

In **red** the primary potential soil health benefit (s) , and if applicable, in **dark yellow** the secondary one(s).

12. **Key references and further reading**

Scan the QR-code which leads to an overview of sources in relation to practices, for international sources as well as sources from France, Ireland, Italy, Spain, and the Netherlands.

2.2 The 35 draft practice sheets

In the following, 35 practices (32+ 6b, 6c, 6d) are described in summary two-pagers. They are often compound practices in the sense that they often involve a variety of ways in which certain core principles can be applied. In relation to cover crops (practice number six) this was so much the case, that we decided to create four variants of the practice sheets.

The descriptions are not meant as the one and only way to understand what these practices are about and how they may be applied. Foremost, they are meant to be a starting point of investigation and decision-making, hopefully in many cases wetting the appetite for consulting other, more detailed and authoritative sources as well.

Descriptions are meant to be useful for a broad readership from at least the five countries from which representatives are involved in writing this catalogue. We do realise, however, that some practices will be more relevant for one country than another. And, it will not always be possible to touch on all relevant specifics and nuances.

These practice sheets will be taken forward by SOILCRATES task 5.4 both in terms of their content and in relation to experiments that SOILCRATES living labs will be engaging in over the next few years.

1. Reduced or non-inversion tillage

Basic description of the practice

Reduced tillage is a soil management practice that minimizes mechanical soil disturbance and can be applied in a variety of ways. The most common approach is non-inversion tillage (no ploughing) or reduced depth of primary tillage, which preserves the soil's natural layering. This enhances soil structure, reduces erosion and runoff by maintaining a stable soil matrix, and creates a rough surface that improves water infiltration. Reduced tillage may also contribute to carbon sequestration by slowing organic matter decomposition. Furthermore, reduced tillage creates a favorable environment for biodiversity and soil life. In Mediterranean conditions, preserving soil moisture is a key objective for this practice. Successful implementation requires effective weed control, proper crop residue management, crop rotation, and measures to prevent soil compaction from heavy machinery. However, challenges include an increased risk of plant-pathogenic fungi and limited suitability for certain soil types and small-seeded crops.

Implementation

1. Choose the right reduced tillage approach based on your crops, soil and available machinery. Plan for a cover crop to improve weed suppression.
2. Assess equipment needs - determine whether new machinery, such as a subsoiler or equipment for cover crop incorporation and seedbed preparation, is required.
3. Adjust your primary tillage timing to match mechanisation and suitable soil conditions. This may differ from traditional ploughing schedules.
4. Monitor and refine your approach to (cover) crop residue incorporation, seedbed preparation and weed management. It may take several years for the soil to reach a new balance and reach the same yields, so be prepared to adapt and learn.

Crops for which relevant

Reduced tillage can be used for various crops but is less suitable for those that require intensive soil disturbance, such as root and tuber crops. It is also challenging for crops that need fine seedbeds and have low weed competitiveness, such as carrots and onions.

Potential impact

On soil physics

+

On soil biology

+

On soil chemistry

+

Potential Impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Climate regulation
- Water regulation
- Erosion control

Supporting/cultural:

- Provision of habitat
- Biodiversity

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

3

Suitable soil

✓	Clay
✓	Sandy
✓	Loamy

Suitable climate

✓	Maritime
✓	Mediterranean
✓	Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

4

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

- Yield reductions may occur initially but generally recover as the soil adapts.
- Weed pressure may increase since ploughing no longer buries weed seeds.
- Implement a smart crop rotation to help manage weed pressure effectively.
- Heavy clay soils and fields with high weed pressure may be unsuitable for reduced tillage. In organic systems the lack of herbicides may cause increased costs for (hand) weeding.
- Direct seeding may be a viable option in fields with adequate soil moisture.
- Soil density may slightly rise, but this is often offset by improved soil stability and aggregation.
- Prevent soil compaction by limiting heavy machinery use, as subsoiling and ploughing will not be available for remediation.

Potential soil health benefit

- ✓ Addressing soil compaction
- ✓ Increasing soil organic matter
- ✓ Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- ✓ Addressing erosion and run-off
- ✓ Improving water management
- ✓ Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- ✓ Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Due to the wide variation in reduced tillage practices, there is a lack of knowledge about its effects in different contexts. Additionally, non-inversion tillage is thought to support carbon sequestration by reducing organic matter decomposition, though its overall impact remains debated. Variations in study results may be due to differences in crop types, organic matter inputs, and climatic conditions across research settings.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

A form of non-inversion tillage. Image © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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2. Creating buffer zone strips

Basic description of the practice

Buffer zone strips are permanently designated areas along the edges of agricultural fields. The plant composition of these strips—often a mixture of grasses, herbs, and flowering species—can vary widely. By intercepting runoff, these uncultivated edges fill the main purpose to improve water quality, particularly by preventing nutrient and sediment flow into nearby ditches. Furthermore they can enhance biodiversity by providing habitat for pollinators, beneficial insects, birds, and small mammals. In addition to supporting wildlife, buffer strips can contribute to natural pest control and potentially reduce the need for pesticides. At the same time, they do take up land that cannot be used for crops. There are different policy requirements regarding buffer zone strips for different EU countries.

Implementation

1. Remove persistent weeds before sowing to reduce competition and give your strip a strong start.
2. Lightly till or harrow the soil to improve seed-to-soil contact, especially on compacted or weedy ground.
3. Pick a strip width that suits your field layout, and choose a flower or grass mix based on your goals, for example, to attract pollinators or reduce erosion. Avoid mixes that might host crop diseases or pests.
4. Choose the right sowing period for your local climate. Calculate the correct seed quantity and apply it evenly using a spreader, seed drill, or by hand. Lightly rake or roll afterward to ensure good soil contact.
5. Time mowing to avoid disturbing birds during their breeding season. In most areas, avoid mowing between mid-March and early August.
6. During the first year, monitor growth and control aggressive weeds if needed. In later years, maintain the strip by mowing once or twice a year, or through light grazing where appropriate.
7. Keep records of what works well such as seed mix, sowing time, and soil preparation in order to improve your approach in future seasons.

Crops for which relevant

Not related to a specific crop in particular.

Potential impact

On soil physics

0

On soil biology

0 +

On soil chemistry

+

Potential Impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Erosion control
- Pollution control
- Pest and disease regulation

Supporting/cultural:

- Provision of habitat
- Biodiversity
- Cultural and non-material elements

Application considerations

Application material cost

●

Application labour cost

●

Effort/knowledge needed

2

Suitable soil

- | | |
|---|-------|
| ✓ | Clay |
| ✓ | Sandy |
| ✓ | Loamy |

Suitable climate

- | | |
|---|---------------|
| ✓ | Maritime |
| ✓ | Mediterranean |
| ✓ | Continental |

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

2

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Buffer strips take up valuable agricultural land. To offset this, consider valorizing the harvested biomass. For example, using the biomass as fertilizer can recycle nutrients back into the soil, improving sustainability.

Additionally, buffer strips planted with attractive flowers can engage the public and raise awareness about biodiversity and sustainable farming practices.

Regular mowing is an effective management tool to limit the spread of unwanted species and maintain the health of the buffer strip.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Research on buffer strips has predominantly focused on their effectiveness in nutrient retention, particularly nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P), in surface runoff. Studies have also explored sediment control and the influence of various vegetation types on this process. Additionally, the impact of buffer strips on biodiversity has been investigated.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Buffer strip with flowers. Image © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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3. Agroforestry

Basic description of the practice

Agroforestry is the purposeful integration of trees or shrubs into farming systems with livestock or arable farming to benefit from their interactions. This practice can involve planting trees within arable fields or grassland, or establishing hedges along field boundaries. The systems' design depends on its intended purpose, such as enhancing natural pest control, generating additional income, fodder production, providing wind protection, or producing biomass for woodchips. The design, in turn, determines the necessary management activities, including tree protection, fertilization, harvesting, and pruning.

Implementation

1. Be aware of national and local laws and regulations regarding tree planting before starting agroforestry.
2. Implementing agroforestry requires careful planning, including tree selection, spacing, and ensuring species compatibility with your crops or livestock. Manage tree-crop competition by selecting tree species that minimize competition for soil moisture (e.g., deep-rooted trees) and light (e.g., consider the shape and height of the tree canopy).
4. Prepare the soil properly before planting (usually in the cool season) to ensure good tree establishment.
5. Monitor the growth of trees and crops regularly, managing pests, diseases, and weeds to maintain a healthy system.
6. Plan for long-term maintenance, including pruning trees to reduce shading or facilitate harvest, and managing undergrowth.
7. Keep records of tree species, planting dates, and management practices to evaluate performance and improve future planning.

Crops for which relevant

Depending on the design, implementing agroforestry is relevant to all types of crops.

Potential impact

On soil physics

+

On soil biology

+

On soil chemistry

+

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Biomass provision
- Climate regulation
- Water regulation
- Erosion control
- Pest and disease regulation

Supporting/cultural:

- Nutrient cycling
- Provision of habitat
- Cultural and non-material elements

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

3

Suitable soil

✓	Clay
✓	Sandy
✓	Loamy

Suitable climate

✓	Maritime
✓	Mediterranean
✓	Continental

Suitable scale of application

1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

2

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Implementing agroforestry can significantly change how your farm looks and operates. Since many aspects of agroforestry are still being researched, be aware of possible impacts on your main crops.

Learning from other farmers is valuable—it helps you adapt agroforestry to fit your farm's style and local environment. Planting trees for harvestable products means you'll need to gain new knowledge and build contacts for marketing.

Also, consider that agroforestry may require additional labor. While it offers sustainable, long-term benefits for the ecosystem, success depends on adapting the system to your local conditions.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Much research highlights the environmental benefits of agroforestry, including better soil health, increased biodiversity, improved water management, and carbon sequestration in specific systems.

However, less attention has been given to how well these systems adapt locally, farmer adoption rates, and their economic viability. More research is needed on the long-term economic benefits, the effects of different tree species on soil health, and how resilient these systems are to climate change.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

© Image from AGFORWARD project, Left: Mixed livestock browsing in holm oak montado, by João Palma, <https://www.flickr.com/photos/agforward/14590076189/in/album-72157642842617165>.

Poplar is planted for timber production, and intercrops are run during the early stages of tree growth, before canopy closure. Piemonte Region (Italy). Photo of P. Paris (CNR IBAF), project Agforword. AIAF (from <https://www.agroforestry.it/foto/nggallery/album/sistemi-silvo-arabili>)

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Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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4. Apply diversified crop rotations

Basic description of the practice

Crop rotation is the practice of growing different types of crops in the same area across sequential seasons or years. A longer and more diverse crop rotation can benefit soil health. Various countries have put in place policy requirements regarding crop rotations. A rotation focusing on cash crops could reduce soil quality, which could be improved by diversifying crop rotations. A more varied cropping system could lower pest and disease pressure, thereby reducing the need for pesticides and enhancing soil health. In addition, for example, grain crops and/or winter cover crops may improve soil health by maintaining soil organic matter, and it has a positive impact on biodiversity in general.

Implementation

1. Decide on the type of crop rotation that fits your farm goals, soil type, and market demand. Choose the order of the crops in the rotation based on nutrient demands, effects on soil structure and soil pests and pathogens.
2. Assess your available machinery to ensure it can handle the tillage, planting, and harvesting requirements of the chosen crops.
3. Develop a fertilization plan tailored to the nutrient needs of each crop in the rotation to maintain soil fertility.
4. Begin with appropriate soil preparation, then proceed with planting or seeding according to the crop schedule.
5. After each harvest, review crop performance, soil health, and pest or disease issues, then adjust your rotation plan as needed to optimize results.

Crops for which relevant

Suitable for intensive cropping systems.

Potential impact

On soil physics

+

On soil biology

+

On soil chemistry

+

Potential Impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Climate regulation
- Water regulation
- Pollution control
- Pest and disease control

Supporting/cultural:

- Nutrient cycling
- Provision of habitat
- Biodiversity

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

2

Suitable soil

✓	Clay
✓	Sandy
✓	Loamy

Suitable climate

✓	Maritime
✓	Mediterranean
✓	Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

2

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Challenges include financial viability. While wider crop rotations can help suppress harmful organisms, choosing the wrong crops or sequences may lead to problems, such as increased risk from pathogens like nematodes. Policy incentives and knowledge-sharing among farmers can support overcoming barriers like complex planning and reduced short-term profits.

Potential soil health benefit

- ✓ Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- ✓ Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- ✓ Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- ✓ Increasing soil cover

Research

Extensive research has been conducted on wider crop rotations and their effects on yields, soil organic matter, nitrogen, and phosphate levels. Studies have also explored crop rotations involving the integration of livestock and arable crops. However, more research is needed on how different crop rotations perform under specific soil conditions, such as drought sensitivity, soil compaction, and impacts on soil life.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Visualisation of a crop rotation with (cover) crops and management practices indicated. Image © Brice Mosa and Violaine Deytieux, 2018.

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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5. Strip cropping

Basic description of the practice

Strip cropping involves growing crops in alternating, narrow strips across a field. It is essentially a form of in-place crop rotation and is well-suited to existing mechanization. Strip widths typically range from 1.5 to 27 meters, with common widths of 3, 6, 9, or 12 meters, depending on machinery size and intended purpose. This system is expected to enhance yields, reduce erosion and pest and disease pressure. Neighboring crops can positively influence each other—through improved light distribution, wind buffering, attraction of natural enemies, and limiting the spread of diseases by reducing direct contamination. In addition, strip cropping supports greater habitat availability for biodiversity due to a more diverse cropping pattern.

Implementation

1. Choose which crops you want to work with and determine the strip width based on the available mechanization. Take into account harvest operations, where you may need to drive into neighboring strips.
2. Create a spatial strip cropping plan that shows which crops will be planted in each strip, ideally over multiple years. Also consider the space needed for headlands and make sure to have a gap year in space so that pests and diseases cannot follow their host crop into the subsequent season.
3. Sow your strips with the selected crops, preferably using GPS for accuracy.
4. Continue managing your crops as you usually manage them in a field, and monitor your field to observe any effects.

Crops for which relevant

Strip cropping suits a variety of crops. Careful planning helps ensure beneficial crop neighbors while avoiding negative interactions like shading or pest issues.

Potential impact	Application considerations									
On soil physics <div style="text-align: center;">0</div>	Application material cost <div style="text-align: center;">○</div>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Suitable soil</th> <th>Suitable climate</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>✓ Clay</td> <td>✓ Maritime</td> </tr> <tr> <td>✓ Sandy</td> <td>✓ Mediterranean</td> </tr> <tr> <td>✓ Loamy</td> <td>✓ Continental</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Suitable soil	Suitable climate	✓ Clay	✓ Maritime	✓ Sandy	✓ Mediterranean	✓ Loamy	✓ Continental
Suitable soil	Suitable climate									
✓ Clay	✓ Maritime									
✓ Sandy	✓ Mediterranean									
✓ Loamy	✓ Continental									
On soil biology <div style="text-align: center;">0</div>	Application labour cost <div style="text-align: center;">● ●</div>	Suitable scale of application <div style="text-align: center;">< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.</div>								
On soil chemistry <div style="text-align: center;">0</div>	Effort/knowledge needed <div style="text-align: center;">3</div>	Extent to which well-researched <div style="text-align: center;">2</div>								
Potential impact on ecosystems services		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p>For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:</p> </div>								
Provisioning/regulating: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Biomass provision ● Erosion control ● Pest and disease regulation 	Supporting/cultural: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provision of habitat ● Biodiversity 									

Further considerations

- In many countries, annual crop registration is required and can be complex for strip cropping systems.
- Other challenges include difficulty in strip-specific management for fertilisation, pesticide application and irrigation. Addressing technical challenges may require investments in specialized equipment.
- Growing crops in strips may make it interesting to explore alternative market opportunities, such as decentralized sales channels and niche markets for diverse crops.
- In the future, the use of autonomous machinery in strip cropping could significantly ease labor demands, making the system more practical.
- Research shows that narrower strips tend to enhance yields and biodiversity, though wider strips are generally more labor-efficient to manage.
- In addition to ecosystem services, strip cropping can also contribute to a more visually appealing landscape.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Ongoing research aims to resolve technical challenges, including the application of irrigation and chemical plant production products. European (Dutch) research so far has focused on yield effects, natural enemies, disease suppression and biodiversity but as each system and context is unique it is difficult to extrapolate the effects to other systems. Internationally and historically, there has been research on systems with only two crops in the US and in less mechanized systems in China.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Potatoes, cereals and other crops in strips. Image © Wageningen University & Research

A strip cropping field where a crop is being harvested. Image © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

6a. Apply cover crops for carbon sequestration

Basic description of the practice

Cover crops (including green manure, catch crops) may have several agro-ecological benefits one of which is carbon sequestration. By definition, carbon sequestration refers to actual reduction of atmospheric CO₂. Cover crops contribute to this by the production of biomass from photosynthesis. The idea of this practice is to select cover crops that are better than others in adding organic matter to the soil. In temperate climates, cover crops may be sown after the main crop harvest in the end of the summer or early autumn. During the winter period growth is restricted. In spring, regrowth can occur in some species. For the purpose of carbon sequestration, the biomass (roots and aboveground) is ploughed under and not harvested. During summer, the biomass will be decomposed, partly ending in stable forms of soil organic matter.

Implementation

1. Select the appropriate cover crop or mixture to maximize carbon sequestration—grasses and winter cereals are particularly effective. Consider factors such as soil type, sowing time, and potential nematode presence.
2. Sow the cover crop and apply fertilizer if needed.
3. Choose an appropriate termination and incorporation method, such as chemical desiccation or mechanical approaches (e.g., ploughing or non-inversion tillage). Note that deep ploughing can reduce carbon sequestration benefits.
4. Evaluate the outcomes and adjust management practices as needed to improve results over time.

Crops for which relevant

Cover crops for carbon sequestration are usually: (winter-) cereals, grass. In principle, this practice is applicable in all arable rotations, especially in early-harvested crops. It is also applicable in the arable phase of a grassland-maize rotation.

Potential impact

On soil physics

+

On soil biology

0

On soil chemistry

+

Application considerations

Application material cost

●

Application labour cost

●

Effort/knowledge needed

2

Suitable soil

✓ Clay

✓ Sandy

✓ Loamy

Suitable climate

✓ Maritime

☐ Mediterranean

✓ Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

3

Potential Impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

● Climate regulation

Supporting/cultural:

● Nutrient cycling
● Provision of habitat

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Cover crops can help reduce certain nematode populations but may also promote the multiplication of others. To support species selection, a host-status scheme is available (Bes4Soil). Additionally, cover crop varieties with resistance to specific plant-parasitic nematodes are available and can contribute to nematode management.

Cover crops can be grown as single species or in mixtures. In colder climates, it is important that the cover crop establishes well before winter. For optimal biomass production, the duration of the growing period should be carefully considered, particularly the timing of sowing and incorporation. Incorporation should be avoided under wet conditions, as this may lead to rotting.

Harvesting/removing the cover crop significantly reduces the return of organic matter to the soil and should be avoided. Ideally, there should be a few weeks between incorporation and the sowing of the main crop. In some cases, nitrogen fertilisation may be needed to prevent nitrogen immobilisation, which could otherwise hinder the growth of the main crop.

Potential soil health benefit

- ✓ Addressing soil compaction
- ✓ Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- ✓ Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- ✓ Closing farm nutrient cycles
- ✓ Improving functional soil biodiversity
- ✓ Improving aboveground biodiversity
- ✓ Increasing soil cover

Research

Extensive research has been conducted on cover crops in the context of climate change, but much of it relies on data from previous decades. Up-to-date information on the actual dry matter production and nitrogen content of individual cover crop species is still lacking and currently pending.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Left: Black oats can accumulate a large amount of biomass. Right: After termination, the organic matter can be incorporated into the soil. Images © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

Funded by
the European Union

6b. Apply cover crops for biological nitrogen fixation

Basic description of the practice

Cover crops may provide several agro-ecological benefits, one of which is biological nitrogen fixation. This is the process by which atmospheric N₂ gas is taken up by Rhizobium bacteria in the root nodules of leguminous plants and converted into organic nitrogen in plant tissues. The idea behind this practice is to choose leguminous cover crops instead of non-leguminous ones. In temperate climates, cover crops are often sown after the main crop harvest in late summer or early autumn. Growth is limited during winter, but some species may regrow in spring. To make the stored nitrogen available, the biomass (roots and aboveground parts) must be incorporated into the soil rather than harvested, or, it may be harvested and transported to another field for incorporation. In either case, the biomass decomposes after incorporation partly contributing to stable soil organic matter and releasing nitrogen to fertilise the main crop.

Implementation

1. Select the appropriate cover crop or mixture with a focus on biological nitrogen fixation, for example, clover, vetch, or other leguminous species. Consider soil type, pH, sowing time, and potential nematode presence.
2. Sow the cover crop and apply fertiliser if needed, but avoid nitrogen fertilisation.
3. Choose an appropriate termination and incorporation method, such as chemical desiccation or mechanical approaches (e.g., ploughing or non-inversion tillage).
4. Evaluate the outcomes and adjust management practices as needed to improve results over time.

Crops for which relevant

Leguminous cover crops, e.g., vetch, red and/or white clover .

Potential impact	Application considerations			
On soil physics <div style="text-align: center;">0</div>	Application material cost <div style="text-align: center;">○</div>	Suitable soil <div style="text-align: center;">✓ Clay</div> <div style="text-align: center;">✓ Sandy</div> <div style="text-align: center;">✓ Loamy</div>	Suitable climate <div style="text-align: center;">✓ Maritime</div> <div style="text-align: center;">✓ Mediterranean</div> <div style="text-align: center;">✓ Continental</div>	
On soil biology <div style="text-align: center;">0</div>	Application labour cost <div style="text-align: center;">○</div>	Suitable scale of application <div style="text-align: center;">< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.</div>		
On soil chemistry <div style="text-align: center;">+</div>	Effort/knowledge needed <div style="text-align: center;">1</div>	Extent to which well-researched <div style="text-align: center;">3</div>		
Potential impact on ecosystems services		For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:		
Provisioning/regulating: ● Nutrient cycling	Supporting/cultural: ● Provision of habitat			

Further considerations

Excess mineral nitrogen in the soil can reduce or inhibit biological nitrogen fixation. This process occurs when plant roots are nodulated by active Rhizobium bacteria. It is generally assumed that Rhizobium is naturally present in agricultural soils. To stimulate bacterial activity and ensure optimal nitrogen fixation, maintaining the right soil pH is important, this may be 0.5 to 1 unit higher than standard recommendations.

Keep in mind that nitrogen from leguminous crops becomes available gradually over the growing season, while mineral nitrogen is available immediately after application.

Leguminous crops are generally more susceptible to certain diseases, such as Aphanomyces and Pythium root rot. Leguminous crops also often moderate to good hosts for plant-parasitic nematodes, including root-knot, root-lesion, and stem nematodes.

Potential soil health benefit

- ✓ Addressing soil compaction
- ✓ Increasing soil organic matter
- ✓ Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- ☐ Addressing erosion and run-off
- ☐ Improving water management
- ✓ Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- ☐ Addressing soil salinisation
- ☐ Addressing soil pollution
- ☐ Suppressing harmful organisms
- ✓ Closing farm nutrient cycles
- ✓ Improving functional soil biodiversity
- ✓ Improving aboveground biodiversity
- ✓ Increasing soil cover

Research

This is a well-researched practice, with available data on nitrogen input per cover crop and the developmental status of different species. However, further research is needed on how the frequency of leguminous crop cultivation affects disease pressure.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Image © Quintarelli et al. 2022. Cover crops for sustainable cropping systems: a review. Agriculture 12(12)

Flowering red clover. Image: © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

Funded by
the European Union

6c. Application of catch crops to reduce nitrogen leaching

Basic description of the practice

Cover crops provide several important agro-ecological benefits, one of which is the ability to capture mineral nitrogen that would otherwise be lost through leaching into deeper soil layers or groundwater. This is particularly important during the winter months, when nitrogen applied earlier in the season can be washed away by rainfall. By growing catch crops during this period, mineral nitrogen is taken up and stored in the plant biomass, effectively preventing nutrient loss. The catch crop is typically grown without additional fertilization, relying on residual soil nutrients. In spring, the cover crop's biomass is incorporated into the soil. As the cover crop decomposes a portion of the nitrogen stored in the cover crop biomass becomes available again for the following.

Implementation

1. Select the appropriate cover crop or mixture with a focus on nitrogen uptake. Consider soil type, pH, sowing time, and potential nematode presence.
2. Sow the cover crop shortly after the main crop harvest or earlier in the season by undersowing. Do not apply nitrogen fertilizer.
3. Choose a suitable termination and incorporation method, such as chemical desiccation or mechanical methods (e.g., ploughing or non-inversion tillage).
4. Adjust the main crop fertilization based on the estimated nitrogen supplied by the incorporated catch crop.
5. Evaluate the results and refine management practices as needed to improve outcomes over time.

Crops for which relevant

Growing a catch crop is especially important after main crops that leave significant amounts of unused nitrogen in the soil or release nitrogen through their residues. In some cases, national regulations may require the use of catch crops to prevent nutrient losses.

Potential impact	Application considerations				
On soil physics <div style="text-align: center;">0</div>	Application material cost <div style="text-align: center;">○</div>	Suitable soil		Suitable climate	
On soil biology <div style="text-align: center;">0</div>	Application labour cost <div style="text-align: center;">○</div>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clay	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sandy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Maritime	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mediterranean
On soil chemistry <div style="text-align: center;">+</div>	Effort/knowledge needed <div style="text-align: center;">1</div>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Loamy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Continental	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable scale of application					
		< 1ha.	1- 10 ha.	10 - 50 ha.	> 50 ha.
Extent to which well-researched					
		3			
Potential Impact on ecosystems services					
Provisioning/regulating:			Supporting/cultural:		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nutrient cycling			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Provision of habitat		
For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:					

Further considerations

In spring, a catch crop that is still actively growing may deplete soil moisture. Depending on weather conditions that year, this can either hinder or benefit the growth of the main crop.

Cover crops can help suppress certain nematode populations but may also promote the multiplication of others. To guide species selection, a host-status scheme is available (<https://www.best4soil.eu/>).

Key considerations for successful use of catch crops include selecting regionally adapted species, ensuring timely sowing and termination, managing soil moisture and fertility, aligning with main crop rotations, and complying with European agri-environmental policies aimed at reducing nitrogen leaching..

Potential soil health benefit

- ✓ Addressing soil compaction
- ✓ Increasing soil organic matter
- ✓ Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- ✓ Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- ✓ Closing farm nutrient cycles
- ✓ Improving functional soil biodiversity
- ✓ Improving aboveground biodiversity
- ✓ Increasing soil cover

Research

It is well known that catch crops are effective to reduce nitrogen leaching, however the effectiveness can vary due to many factors. Key research gaps include identifying the best species and mixtures for different conditions, optimizing timing and management, understanding long-term soil health effects and integrating catch crops with other farming practices.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Image © Liu, 2013. Phosphorus Leaching as Influenced by Animal Manure and Catch Crops.

Undersowing of grass catch crop in maize
Image © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

6d. Apply selected cover crops for nematode control

Basic description of the practice

Cover crops provide several important agro-ecological benefits, but careful selection is essential to avoid increasing the risk of a nematode outbreak. A well-chosen green manure crop can help suppress plant-parasitic nematodes. However, using unsuitable species, particularly those that serve as hosts to harmful nematodes such as certain brassicas or legumes, can lead to a build-up of nematode populations in the soil. This risk is heightened in systems with limited crop rotation or repeated use of susceptible cover crops. Additional contributing factors include poorly timed termination, which allows nematodes to continue reproducing, and low species diversity in the rotation, which can favor the dominance of specific nematode species.

Implementation

1. Select the appropriate cover crop or mixture based on nematode host status. Use available host-status schemes to avoid species that support harmful nematodes. Best4Soil can be accessed via this link: <https://nematodeschema.soilhealthtool.eu/en-gb/Nematode-scheme>
Consider compatibility with the full crop rotation, soil type, pH, and sowing time.
2. Sow the cover crop and apply fertilizer if needed.
3. Choose an appropriate termination and incorporation method, such as chemical desiccation or mechanical approaches (e.g., ploughing or non-inversion tillage), ensuring timely destruction before nematodes can complete another reproduction cycle.
4. Monitor nematode presence and crop performance. Adjust cover crop species, rotation order, or management practices as needed to reduce nematode pressure over time.

Crops for which relevant

No crops in particular other than those that suffer yield and/or quality loss due to plant parasitic nematodes.

Potential impact

On soil physics

0

On soil biology

++

On soil chemistry

0

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

● Pest and disease control

Supporting/cultural:

● Provision of habitat

Application considerations

Application material cost

○

Application labour cost

●

Effort/knowledge needed

3

Suitable soil

✓ Clay

✓ Sandy

✓ Loamy

Suitable climate

✓ Maritime

□ Mediterranean

□ Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

4

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Key considerations for managing nematodes with cover crops include selecting non-host species, understanding local nematode populations, and ensuring timely termination of the cover crop. Rotating suppressive and non-host species within the cropping system helps break nematode life cycles and reduce population pressure. Known host species should be avoided in fields with high nematode levels. Soil testing before cover crop selection is recommended to inform species choice and improve nematode management.

Commonly used nematode-resistant or suppressive cover crop types include:

Brassicaceae (mustard family): These plants contain glucosinolates that break down into isothiocyanates, compounds known to suppress nematodes.

Grasses (cereals): Generally non-hosts to nematodes, grasses help reduce nematode populations by limiting their food sources.

Legumes: While some legumes can host nematodes, careful selection of specific species can help manage nematode pressure effectively.

Potential soil health benefit

- ✓ Addressing soil compaction
- ✓ Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- ✓ Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- ✓ Suppressing harmful organisms
- ✓ Closing farm nutrient cycles
- ✓ Improving functional soil biodiversity
- ✓ Improving aboveground biodiversity
- ✓ Increasing soil cover

Research

Although a lot of valuable knowledge is available, the host status of many common cover crop species is still not fully known, especially for all relevant species across different soil types and environmental conditions. Further research is needed to better understand how various cover crops interact with nematode populations in diverse cropping systems.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

White mustard mechanical termination. Image: © Wageningen University

Best4Soil nematode tool landing page (<https://www.best4soil.eu/>). Screenshot image: © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

7. Intercropping

Basic description of the practice

Intercropping is an agricultural practice in which two or more crops are grown simultaneously on the same land. The main goal is to optimize resource use such as sunlight, water, and nutrients and enhance productivity per unit area. Strategic combinations of species, for example deep- and shallow-rooted plants, maximize complementary interactions and improve soil resource efficiency. Legumes intercropped with other crops can fix nitrogen, reducing the need for synthetic fertilizers while improving yield and protein content, especially in organic systems. Seed rates in intercrops often total more than 100 percent compared to sole cropping. Intercropping generally results in a higher Land Equivalent Ratio (LER), indicating more efficient land use than monocultures. Additionally, it supports biodiversity by providing habitats for beneficial insects and may also reduce weed, pest, and disease pressures, lower input costs, and increases resilience to environmental stresses.

Implementation

1. Determine the goal: Clearly define the purpose of the mixed cropping system, such as improving soil health, pest control, protein content, or maximizing yield.
2. Select crops with complementary growth cycles: Choose crops with different growth patterns to maximize the use of space and resources throughout the growing season.
3. Check for suitable mechanization: Ensure that appropriate machinery is available. Sowing may need to be done in two stages or require adjusted equipment. Consider mechanization options for efficiently separating the crops after harvest, if needed.
4. Ensure broad sowing for weed suppression: Use dense sowing techniques to effectively suppress weeds and reduce competition for nutrients, water, and light.
5. Monitor and evaluate: Regularly assess crop growth, pest and weed pressure, and overall system performance. Use these insights to adjust management practices and improve outcomes in future seasons.

Crops for which relevant

Intercropping can be used with all crops but is most common with maize and catch crops; cereals with legumes; rapeseed with beans or clover; and grasses undersown in cereals.

Potential impact

On soil physics

+

On soil biology

+

On soil chemistry

+

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

2

Suitable soil

✓	Clay
✓	Sandy
✓	Loamy

Suitable climate

✓	Maritime
✓	Mediterranean
✓	Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha.	1 - 10 ha.	10 - 50 ha.	> 50 ha.
--------	------------	-------------	----------

Extent to which well-researched

3

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

● Biomass provision

Supporting/cultural:

● Nutrient cycling
● Provision of habitat

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

- Herbicide and pesticide options for intercropping are limited.
- Challenges also include mechanization, uneven crop ripening, separating mixed harvests, and market uncertainties.
- Managing soil diseases through crop rotation becomes more difficult, with increased risks of nematode and fungal populations.
- A related practice is mixing cultivars of the same species, aiming to improve yield stability, resilience, and risk management.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Intercropping and cover cropping have been widely researched, but many questions remain unanswered. The effects of specific crop combinations are often only partially quantified, and lessons from well-studied systems are sometimes overlooked in new research. Additionally, the relevance of findings to common agricultural practices is not always considered. Overall, evidence tends to be limited, with effects usually neutral or only slightly positive. The impact on soil-borne pathogens and nematodes remains poorly studied. Further research is also needed on developing crop varieties with more uniform ripening to improve management in mixed systems.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Experiment with legume and cereal intercropping. Image © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

Funded by
the European Union

8. Application of Tagetes for nematode control

Basic description of the practice

Cover crops may have several agro-ecological benefits (see factsheets 6a–d), one of which is nematode control. Cultivating marigolds (*Tagetes patula*) can significantly reduce populations of the plant-parasitic nematode *Pratylenchus penetrans*. Additionally, it is not a host for other nematode species. This nematode affects many crops, including potato, maize, onion, and sugar beet. For effective control, *Tagetes* should remain on the field for at least 3 to 4 months, with good biomass development and without weeds, as weeds may also serve as hosts for *P. penetrans*.

Implementation

1. Use *Tagetes* selectively in crop rotations that include economically important crops affected by *Pratylenchus penetrans*.
2. Sow *Tagetes* on time to allow for at least 3–4 months of growth before frost, as it is highly frost-sensitive. Note that sowing may require specialised equipment due to the small and irregular shape of the seeds.
3. Fertilise if necessary and manage weeds carefully, especially during early growth when *Tagetes* is slow to establish.
4. Allow natural frost termination, after which the biomass can be incorporated into the soil using standard tillage practices.
5. Evaluate the impact on crop yields and soil health. *Tagetes* effectively reduces *P. penetrans* populations, with benefits lasting 3–6 years.

Crops for which relevant

Cropping plans that include high value crops sensitive to *Pratylenchus penetrans* such as onions, flower bulbs, strawberries, potatoes, roses and tree nursery crops.

Potential impact

On soil physics

0 +

On soil biology

+

On soil chemistry

0 +

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

Supporting/cultural:

- Biomass provision
- Pest and disease regulation

Application considerations

Application material cost

●

Application labour cost

○

Effort/knowledge needed

2

Suitable soil

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|-------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Clay |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Sandy |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Loamy |

Suitable climate

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|---------------|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Maritime |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Mediterranean |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Continental |

Suitable scale of application

< 1 ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

3

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Species Selection: Not all *Tagetes* species work equally well. *Tagetes patula* and *Tagetes erecta* are proven to suppress root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.) and lesion nematodes (*Pratylenchus* spp.) by producing natural nematicidal compounds called thiophenes in their roots.

Sufficient Biomass and Root Contact: The nematicidal effect depends on having high root density and biomass, as the active compounds come from root exudates. Good crop establishment and enough growing time are critical.

Climate and Seasonality: *Tagetes* is sensitive to frost and low temperatures, so it's best used in warmer months or milder climates. It is not suited as an overwintering cover crop.

Timing in Crop Rotation: Plant *Tagetes* between main crops when nematodes are active. It works best grown before a susceptible crop to break the nematode lifecycle. It can also be combined with a short-term crop.

Field History and Monitoring: Test soil to confirm the presence of *P. penetrans*. Avoid repeated monoculture use to prevent resistance buildup.

Potential soil health benefit

- ✓ Addressing soil compaction
- ✓ Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- ✓ Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- ✓ Suppressing harmful organisms
- ✓ Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- ✓ Improving aboveground biodiversity
- ✓ Increasing soil cover

Research

Research has confirmed that *Tagetes* is an effective and long-term measure against *P. penetrans* and acts as a non-host for many other nematode species. The underlying mechanisms for its nematode-suppressive effects have also been studied. However, the host status of *Tagetes* is not yet fully known for all nematode species or other soil pathogens. Economic studies have shown that growing *Tagetes* can be financially viable, sometimes even as a replacement for a main crop. There is still limited knowledge regarding its influence on other soil organisms and its effectiveness under different soil conditions.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Tagetes patula grown on a sandy soil for the benefit of starch potato yields. Images © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025
Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus
Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

9. Species diversification in grassland

Basic description of the practice

Cultivating herb-rich grassland may provide multiple benefits such as improved cow health, higher milk production with increased protein content, and enhanced water uptake and infiltration due to species with varied rooting depths. Leguminous plants like clover also contribute by fixing nitrogen. The species diversity supports biodiversity, climate resilience, and environmental quality. By diversifying grasslands, farmers can improve forage resilience and quality, reduce reliance on fertilizers, and promote healthier soils and animals, which are key advantages amid changing climate and market conditions.

Implementation

1. Decide whether to overseed or reseed based on factors like weed presence (e.g., couch grass) and soil quality. For reseeding, select the right timing and suitable methods for destroying existing grass and preparing the soil.
2. Select the appropriate herb species mixture.
3. Before overseeding graze tightly or take a cut of silage. Follow the supplier's recommendations for herb fertilization and sowing.
4. Graze again for up to 10 days to keep the sward short and afterwards also maintain relatively short.

Image © DeCock et al. 2022. Ecosystem multifunctionality lowers as grasslands under restoration approach their target habitat type

Crops for which relevant

Monocultures of grass, e.g., English ryegrass.

Potential impact

On soil physics

+

On soil biology

+

On soil chemistry

+

Application considerations

Application material cost

●

Application labour cost

●

Effort/knowledge needed

2

Suitable soil

✓ Clay
✓ Sandy
✓ Loamy

Suitable climate

✓ Maritime
✓ Mediterranean
✓ Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

3

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Biomass provision
- Climate regulation
- Water regulation

Supporting/cultural:

- Nutrient cycling
- Provision of habitat
 - Biodiversity
- Cultural and non-material elements

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Establishing white clover in grass takes time and typically involves both reseeding and over sowing. Full reseeding is the most reliable method while over sowing is a simpler low cost option. Success depends heavily on soil fertility, weather during sowing, and post sowing grazing management.

Mixtures can include various grasses, nitrogen fixing legumes, and herbs so effects may vary. It is important to consider feed value such as protein, energy content, and palatability within the cows' diet. Note that herb proportions usually decline over time especially in fertile soils and chemical weed control options are limited.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water**
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles**
- Improving functional soil biodiversity**
- Improving aboveground biodiversity**
- Increasing soil cover

Research

The transfer of nitrogen from clover to grass is well researched, and mixtures can be extended to include species adapted to drought conditions. Research on species diversification in European dairy grasslands shows that incorporating legumes and deep-rooted herbs such as chicory and plantain improves forage yield, enhances drought resilience, increases nitrogen use efficiency, supports pollinators, and reduces reliance on synthetic fertilizers.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

A herb rich grassland with yellow flowers. Image © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

Funded by
the European Union

10. Application of compost

Basic description of the practice

Applying compost is a straightforward way to improve soil health by adding organic matter, which feeds soil life and supplies nutrients. Organic matter plays a key role in essential soil functions such as maintaining soil structure and aggregation, enhancing water retention and purification, and supporting nutrient cycling. Applying compost at the scale of the crop rotation contributes to long-term soil health and resilience.

Implementation

1. Choose the right time to apply compost, either in spring or autumn, depending on the crop rotation. Avoid applying compost just before nitrogen-demanding crops such as potatoes.
2. Select compost of good quality, preferably with a certification label and available analysis of its contents.
3. Determine how much compost to apply based on the organic matter content of both the compost and the soil. Application rates usually range from 10 to 25 tonnes per hectare.
3. Adjust the mineral fertilisation plan of the main crop to reflect the additional nutrients provided by the compost and the expected mineralisation into plant-available forms.
4. Use a manure-spreader for topsoil application and lightly incorporate into the soil by tillage.

Crops for which relevant

Compost is a soil amendment suited for all crops in the rotation.

Potential impact

On soil physics

+

On soil biology

+

On soil chemistry

+

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

1

Suitable soil

✓	Clay
✓	Sandy
✓	Loamy

Suitable climate

✓	Maritime
✓	Mediterranean
✓	Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

4

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Biomass provision
- Climate regulation
- Water regulation

Supporting/cultural:

- Nutrient cycling
- Biodiversity

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Effects on crop yields and soil health will mainly be apparent on soils with low fertility.

Compost effects vary depending on the type and ripeness. Unripe or lignin-rich composts can temporarily immobilise nitrogen. It is important to check compost quality, certification, and content to avoid contamination with glass, microplastics, PFAS, or heavy metals. Selection should consider availability, cost, and possible alternatives such as farmyard manure, digestate, or straw.

Green waste compost improves soil structure and adds organic matter, but is generally low in nutrients. Manure-based compost is rich in nitrogen and phosphorus, making it suitable for building soil fertility. Food waste compost is also nutrient-rich and increasingly used in circular agriculture. Municipal solid waste compost can be applied under strict quality control, but may pose risks of contamination and salinisation.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Most research on composts tends to focus either on short-term or long-term effects, but field experiments are needed to develop advisory systems that integrate both perspectives. Current studies explore how different compost types such as manure-based, green waste, and vermicompost influence soil microbial activity, nutrient availability, carbon storage, and crop yield. They also evaluate contamination risks like plastics and heavy metals and assess the role of compost in sustainable nutrient recycling.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Compost being spread after a maize harvest. Image © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

Funded by
the European Union

11. Application of bokashi

Basic description of the practice

Bokashi is an organic soil amendment that can be applied directly to the soil. The term refers to a specific fermentation process of organic residues. During this anaerobic fermentation, the temperature rises to around 40 degrees Celsius, which can help eliminate some weed seeds and pathogens. Bokashi serves as a source of nutrients and a soil improver, offering a way to upgrade local organic biomass residues effectively.

Implementation

To produce Bokashi:

1. Collect the raw materials. Anything can be used, from ditch and roadside clippings to leaves and crop residues.
2. Mix the source material with lime, then moisten with a solution of effective micro-organisms, then solidify and cover with plastic.
3. After about eight to ten weeks of fermentation, the product is 'ripe' and the silage can be reopened. The end-product would have a carbon to nitrogen ratio between 15:1 and 25:1 and humidity between 40 and 50 percent.

To apply Bokashi:

4. Have the Bokashi analysed for nutrients and organic matter content.
5. Choose the right time to apply, in spring or autumn, taking into account the crop rotation.
6. Choose the amount to apply based on the nutrient and/or organic matter contents.
7. Adapt mineral fertilisation of the main crop to the nutrients applied with Bokashi and their expected period of mineralisation into plant available forms.
8. Use a manure-spreader for topsoil application and lightly incorporate into the soil by tillage.

Crops for which relevant

Bokashi is soil amendment suited for all crops in the rotation.

Potential impact

On soil physics

0 +

On soil biology

0 +

On soil chemistry

0 +

Potential Impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Climate regulation
- Water regulation

Supporting/cultural:

- Nutrient cycling
- Biodiversity

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

2 3

Suitable soil

✓	Clay	✓	Maritime
✓	Sandy	✓	Mediterranean
✓	Loamy	✓	Continental

Suitable climate

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

1 2

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Bokashi can be more labor-intensive and costly compared to other soil amendments, so it's important to weigh it against alternatives such as farm-yard manure, digestate, or straw. To use bokashi effectively, select suitable organic materials like food waste or manure, ferment them under airtight anaerobic conditions with microbial inoculants (e.g., effective microorganisms or lactobacillus), allow proper post-fermentation maturation, and apply it at the right time to prevent nitrogen immobilization. In cooler climates, extending the fermentation period by 2 to 4 weeks, insulating the bokashi bins, or storing them in a frost-free area may be necessary.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter**
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water**
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles**
- Improving functional soil biodiversity**
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

It is not yet clear whether diseases and weeds are effectively killed during bokashi fermentation. Some observations suggest that incorporating bokashi into clay soils can lead to oxygen depletion, which requires further research to understand and to develop methods to prevent this issue.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Bokashi Image © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

Funded by
the European Union

12. Application of biochar

Basic description of the practice

Biochar is produced by pyrolysis of organic biomass at high temperatures with little oxygen and is available in different types and shapes such as woodchips up to microgranules. It is considered a soil amendment of which the decay is retarded due to the pyrolysis process. Biochar can be made of different organic materials such as straw, wood and several other organic materials. Applying biochar will mainly contribute to carbon sequestration since its decay is retarded for decades and it may stay in soils for centuries. Additional positive effects may be possible on crop growth, water use, soil life and emissions.

Implementation

1. Select the type and dosage of biochar based on the measured contents of both the biochar and the soil to be amended. The application rate should be determined according to the intended purpose of the biochar.
2. Apply the biochar by spreading it evenly on the soil surface, for example using a solid manure spreader or a mineral fertiliser spreader, depending on the type.
3. After spreading, incorporate the biochar into the soil through mixing or tilling.
4. Monitor the effects of the biochar application on soil properties and crop performance over the following years.

Crops for which relevant

As biochar is a long-term soil amendment, it is applicable to a wide variety of crops.

Potential impact

On soil physics

0 +

On soil biology

0 +

On soil chemistry

0 +

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

1

Suitable soil

✓	Clay
✓	Sandy
✓	Loamy

Suitable climate

✓	Maritime
✓	Mediterranean
✓	Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

2

Potential Impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Climate regulation
- Water regulation
- Erosion control

Supporting/cultural:

- Nutrient cycling
- Biodiversity

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

A large meta-analysis has shown that biochar application can lead to improved water use efficiency, enhanced microbial activity, increased soil organic carbon, and reduced greenhouse gas emissions. However, the effects can vary between soils of different fertility. Moreover, the quality of the biochar plays a critical role: if the pyrolysis process is incomplete or if low-quality organic material is used, the resulting biochar may contain contaminants or have high salinity, potentially leading to negative effects on soil and crops.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter**
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management**
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution**
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity**
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Biochar has received significant attention for its potential in carbon sequestration, owing to its highly retarded rate of decay. Research is actively exploring how biochar derived from various feedstocks (e.g., wood, manure) influences soil pH, nutrient retention, microbial activity, and greenhouse gas emissions. Current research frontiers include tailoring biochar properties to specific soil types and crop needs, co-applying it with compost or digestate, and integrating biochar use into broader carbon farming strategies.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Biochar in a bag. Image from USDA Forest Service photo by Deborah Page-Dumroese
<https://www.flickr.com/photos/usdagov/48365280617/>

Source: Dorjee et al. 2024. Biochar: A Comprehensive Review on a Natural Approach to Plant Disease Management. J Pure Appl Microbiol 18(1):29-45.

Date: June 2025

Authors: Lena Madden, Hina Imtiaz, Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

Funded by
the European Union

13. Application of seaweed products

Basic description of the practice

Seaweed, whether fresh, dried or processed, can be used directly as mulch, composted, or turned into liquid fertilizer and biostimulants. Different seaweed species and processing methods result in a variety of products, each with distinct effects. Depending on the type used, seaweed can improve moisture retention, suppress pests, and enhance plant resistance to disease. In coastal regions of Ireland, Spain, Italy and the Netherlands, farmers have traditionally collected and applied seaweed to enrich sandy or degraded soils, making it a long-standing agricultural practice.

Implementation

1. Define agronomic objectives: Set clear goals for your seaweed use, such as improving stress tolerance, nutrient uptake, or yield. Confirm that the seaweed products are suitable for your crops and farming system.
2. Select appropriate seaweed species and products: Choose products based on their intended use and ensure they comply with safety and quality standards. Follow the producer's dosage recommendations.
3. Determine application method and timing: Apply seaweed products via foliar spray, soil drench, seed treatment, or coated fertilizer, depending on product type and available equipment. Time applications during key growth stages or periods of stress.
4. Integrate with existing fertilisation: Coordinate seaweed application with current fertilization practices to optimize benefits and avoid overuse.
5. Monitor and evaluate outcomes: Track crop performance and soil health after application, adjusting dosage or timing as needed.

Crops for which relevant

Application of seaweed is suitable for various crops.

Potential impact

On soil physics

0 +

On soil biology

0 +

On soil chemistry

0

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Climate regulation
- Water regulation

Supporting/cultural:

- Nutrient cycling
- Biodiversity

Application considerations

Application material cost

●

Application labour cost

●

Effort/knowledge needed

2

Suitable soil

- ✓ Clay
- ✓ Sandy
- ✓ Loamy

Suitable climate

- ✓ Maritime
- ✓ Mediterranean
- ✓ Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

2

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

- When applying seaweed in European agriculture, success depends on selecting the right species. Typically, brown seaweeds such as *Ascophyllum nodosum* or *Laminaria digitata* are used because they are rich in bioactive compounds like alginates, cytokinins, and betaines. These compounds can improve plant stress tolerance, root development, and nutrient uptake. In the near future, the use of nitrogen fertilizers and synthetic pesticides may decrease, making seaweed products an important option for maintaining plant health.

- Unprocessed seaweed collected directly from the sea may not be suitable as fertilizer due to its high salt content.

- It is important to use sustainably harvested or farmed seaweed to avoid ecological harm, especially in coastal areas protected by EU marine regulations.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

There is a lot of research on applying seaweed and seaweed-based products. However, significant gaps remain regarding long-term effects, economic feasibility, optimal application rates, crop species-specific benefits, and broader ecological impacts. The exact mode of action of seaweed on plants is also not yet fully understood.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Examples of a seaweed containing products for agricultural use. Image on the left © <https://www.bioatlantis.com/> Image on the right © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Lena Madden, Hina Imtiaz, Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

14. Digestate

Basic description of the practice

Digestate is a by-product of anaerobic digestion, a natural process in which microorganisms break down organic materials such as manure, crop residues, or grass to produce biogas. This process produces both a liquid and a solid fraction of digestate, with the liquid fraction being the most nutrient-available. Digestate is a nutrient-rich fertilizer containing nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, with a higher proportion of mineral nutrients compared to the original organic material. It also contains significantly reduced levels of pathogens and weed seeds compared to the source material. Like other organic fertilizers, digestate can improve soil structure, increase moisture retention, and support microbial activity, which may contribute to higher crop yields, especially on soils with low fertility.

Implementation

1. Define your objective for using digestate based on soil analysis and crop requirements.
2. Select an appropriate digestate with known nutrient content that fits your fertilization plan. Adjust the plan if necessary according to the digestate's nutrient levels. Liquid digestate supplies nutrients readily and is suitable for immediate uptake, while solid digestate is rich in organic matter and improves soil structure and long-term fertility.
3. Choose the right time to apply digestate, typically in spring or summer, considering nitrogen mineralization and plant uptake. Avoid application during heavy rainfall or on frozen ground to reduce runoff risk.
4. Apply digestate preferably by injecting it into the soil to minimize ammonia volatilization and odor, and to place nutrients closer to plant roots.
5. Monitor and evaluate outcomes to assess effects on soil health and crop performance.

Crops for which relevant

Application of digestate is suitable for various crops.

Potential impact

On soil physics

0 +

On soil biology

- 0 +

On soil chemistry

0 +

Potential Impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Climate regulation
- Water regulation

Supporting/cultural:

- Nutrient cycling
- Biodiversity

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

1

Suitable soil

✓	Clay
✓	Sandy
✓	Loamy

Suitable climate

✓	Maritime
✓	Mediterranean
✓	Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

2

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Digestate is a by-product of biogas production, which itself is an alternative to fossil fuels. Furthermore, digestate serves as a useful substitute for mineral fertilizers that do not contribute to soil organic matter and require high energy inputs to produce.

However, the soil benefits of digestate may not exceed those of organic fertilizers in general, as its organic matter content can be lower. Compared to mineral fertilizers, digestate provides soil health benefits similar to other organic fertilizers. For improving soil health, using the original organic material before biogas production, which contains a higher fraction of organic matter, would be preferable if risks for contamination, pathogens and weed seeds are not an issue.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter**
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management**
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles**
- Improving functional soil biodiversity**
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Digestate has been well researched as a renewable fertilizer, which is its main purpose. Depending on its exact composition, we can assess its value for soils and crops, similar to other organic fertilizers. Further research could focus on how variations in digestate composition, dosage, soil types, and crops affect yields and environmental impacts.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Digestate production installation. Image © Wageningen University & Research

Digestate can be injected into the soil to reduce volatilization. Image © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Barra Caracciolo A, Grenni P, Narciso A, De Carolis C, Ancona V, Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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15. Clay minerals and rock-based materials

Basic description of the practice

Farmers can improve soil quality by applying clay minerals and rock-based amendments in various forms such as vermiculite, lava split, bentonite, and clinoptilolite, a type of zeolite. These materials help enhance soil structure, water retention, and nutrient availability. Vermiculite and bentonite increase water-holding capacity, especially in sandy soils, while clinoptilolite binds cations. Lava split improves aeration and drainage in heavy soils. Usually mixed into the topsoil, these amendments support sustainable, low-input farming systems, particularly in dry regions or where soil health restoration is needed.

Implementation

1. Determine the objective of clay mineral application based on soil measurements such as soil texture, nutrient levels, and water-holding capacity.
2. Select an appropriate amendment based on the set objective and clay mineral characteristics.
3. Determine application rates by following manufacturer recommendations, typically ranging from 1 to 5 tons per hectare depending on soil conditions.
4. Spread the clay mineral evenly over the field.
5. Incorporate the amendments into the topsoil using tillage equipment to ensure even distribution.
6. Monitor and evaluate outcomes through soil testing, observing crop performance, and adjusting practices as needed.

Crops for which relevant

Since clay minerals are soil amendments, their application is suitable for all crops.

Potential impact	Application considerations				
On soil physics <div style="text-align: right; font-weight: bold;">+</div>	Application material cost <div style="text-align: right; font-weight: bold;">●</div>	Suitable soil		Suitable climate	
		✓ Clay	✓	Maritime	
		✓ Sandy	✓	Mediterranean	
		✓ Loamy	✓	Continental	
On soil biology <div style="text-align: right; font-weight: bold;">0</div>	Application labour cost <div style="text-align: right; font-weight: bold;">●</div>	Suitable scale of application			
		< 1ha.	1- 10 ha.	10 - 50 ha.	> 50 ha.
On soil chemistry <div style="text-align: right; font-weight: bold;">+</div>	Effort/knowledge needed <div style="text-align: right; font-weight: bold;">1</div>	Extent to which well-researched			
		1			
Potential impact on ecosystems services					
Provisioning/regulating:			Supporting/cultural:		
<input type="checkbox"/> Water regulation <input type="checkbox"/> Pollution control			<input type="checkbox"/> Nutrient cycling		
For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:					

Further considerations

Clay minerals have different functions, so it is important to apply the right type based on the specific site. Vermiculite can increase water retention in sandy soils. Lava split enhances aeration and drainage in heavy clay soils. Bentonite improves water-holding capacity and cation exchange in sandy soils. Clinoptilolite, a type of zeolite, aids nutrient retention by binding cations. Avoid over-application to prevent mineral imbalances or soil compaction, especially with fine clays like bentonite.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Research has explored the effects of clay minerals on drought resilience, nutrient retention, and soil microbiota. Some studies on mineral soils have measured impacts on yield, but results remain inconclusive. Key research gaps include long-term field performance, optimal application rates for different soil types, interactions with organic amendments, and scalability.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Images of clay minerals and lava grit © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

16. Application of wood ash

Basic description of the practice

Wood ash, rich in potassium, calcium, and trace minerals, serves as a natural fertilizer. It raises soil pH, making it especially beneficial for acidic soils by neutralizing soil acidity. Next to its liming effects it may also positively influence soil structure and water retention. Farmers in many countries have traditionally used wood ash to improve soil quality, often recycling ash from wood burning in heating or cooking. However, its application should be managed carefully to avoid excessive alkalinity or potential heavy metal accumulation, depending on the ash source.

Implementation

1. Measure the soil pH and mineral levels, as well as the alkalinity and mineral content of the wood ash.
2. Determine the appropriate application rate based on soil and ash analysis, considering the crop's pH requirements.
3. Spread the wood ash evenly over the field using a lime spreader.
4. Incorporate the ash into the topsoil promptly using a cultivator or harrow to minimize wind drift and ensure even mixing.
5. Monitor the effects of the application on soil properties and crop performance.

Crops for which relevant

Wood ash is most suitable for crops that require potassium and thrive in alkaline soil conditions.

Potential impact

On soil physics

0

On soil biology

0

On soil chemistry

+

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Biomass provision
- Water regulation

Supporting/cultural:

- Nutrient cycling

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

1

Suitable soil

✓	Clay
✓	Sandy
✓	Loamy

Suitable climate

✓	Maritime
✓	Mediterranean
✓	Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1 ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

3

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

The mineral content of wood ash varies depending on the type of organic material used for its production. Wood ash provides beneficial minerals such as magnesium and calcium; however, it does not contain nitrogen, so additional artificial or organic fertilizers may be necessary. Keep in mind that not all micronutrients in the ash are readily available for plant uptake. It is important to avoid using ash from treated or painted wood, as it may contain harmful substances.

Wood ash is not an EU-approved fertilizer or soil amendment, although some exceptions may exist at the national level. There may also be regulations to prevent overuse, as excessive application can lead to heavy metal buildup in soils.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Research consistently shows that wood ash can improve soil water retention and structure, provide nutrients, and act as an effective liming agent, leading to better crop growth and yield in cases where these issues are limiting the yields. The effect of wood ash on agricultural soils can be accurately predicted based on its mineral composition. Despite this, guidelines for its use and production in agriculture are often lacking.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Wood ash photographed from nearby. Image © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Lena Madden, Hina Imtiaz, Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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17. Application of gypsum for soil structure

Basic description of the practice

Adding gypsum to agricultural soils can increase calcium availability and improve soil structure, making it especially useful for crops like potatoes. Structural problems in heavy clay soils often arise from low calcium occupancy on the clay-humus complex or excessive sodium occupancy. High sodium levels usually occur on fields affected by salinity due to saline seepage or irrigation water. This imbalance reduces soil crumbability and weakens soil structure, leading to more soil clods during harvesting and increased tare. Gypsum supplies calcium, which replaces sodium on soil particles, helping to restore soil structure and improve overall soil quality.

Implementation

1. Identify parcels suffering from structure problems due to sodium through soil measurements or practical experience.
2. Test soil sodium and calcium levels to confirm the need for gypsum and help fine-tune the dosage.
3. Determine the dosage of gypsum. Usual application levels are 2 to 3 tonnes per hectare depending on soil heaviness and gypsum type.
4. Spread the gypsum on the field using a broadcast spreader, preferably after planting potatoes but before the furrow is built.
5. Monitor soil structure and crop performance after application to assess improvements.

Crops for which relevant

Gypsum is especially valuable for potatoes grown on soils with structure problems because it improves soil crumbability, leading to easier harvest and potentially reducing tare.

Potential impact	Application considerations				
On soil physics <div style="text-align: right;">+</div>	Application material cost <div style="text-align: center;">●</div>	Suitable soil		Suitable climate	
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clay	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Maritime		
		<input type="checkbox"/> Sandy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mediterranean		
		<input type="checkbox"/> Loamy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Continental		
On soil biology <div style="text-align: center;">0</div>	Application labour cost <div style="text-align: center;">●</div>	Suitable scale of application			
		< 1ha.	1 - 10 ha.	10 - 50 ha.	> 50 ha.
On soil chemistry <div style="text-align: center;">0</div>	Effort/knowledge needed <div style="text-align: center;">1</div>	Extent to which well-researched			
		<div style="text-align: center;">1</div>			
Potential impact on ecosystems services					
Provisioning/regulating:		Supporting/cultural:			
<input type="checkbox"/> Biomass provision		<input type="checkbox"/> Nutrient cycling			
		<input type="checkbox"/> Water regulation			
For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:					

Further considerations

Next to improving soil structure, the addition of gypsum also provides calcium and sulphur which may benefit crop growth, especially in acidic and low-fertility soils.

On fields with severe issues, such as heavy clay soils with very poor structure or problems caused by saline seepage, gypsum application may have limited effect. Applying large amounts of gypsum can lead to high sulphate levels that may leach into groundwater. Although there are currently no regulations on sulphur, such rules may be introduced in the future.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- ✓ Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- ✓ Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- ✓ Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Gypsum is widely studied as a soil amendment, especially for improving soil structure in problematic soils such as heavy clays and saline-sodic soils. There is more research needed on the effect of sulphur on leaching and effects on soil life.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

A pile of gypsum for agricultural use. Image © Wageningen University & Research

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Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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18. Microbial biostimulants

Basic description of the practice

Microbial biostimulants can enhance soil health by introducing beneficial microorganisms that improve nutrient availability, root growth, and soil structure. Products include compost tea, extracellular polymers, mycorrhizal fungi, and microbial consortia. They are applied as seed coatings, root drenches, or foliar sprays, often alongside organic matter or fertilizers to boost effectiveness.

Their success depends on matching the product to the soil and crop, and ensuring adequate moisture and aeration. Biostimulants support nutrient cycling, plant-microbe interactions, and pathogen suppression, while also stimulating root exudates that promote microbial diversity and soil aggregation.

Implementation

1. Choose the biostimulant based on specific challenges on your farm (e.g. poor root growth, low nutrient availability, or soil structure issues).
2. Apply using the appropriate method, such as seed coating, root dipping, or mixing with irrigation water, depending on the product.
3. Avoid compacted, saline, or waterlogged soils, as these conditions can reduce effectiveness.
4. Monitor and evaluate outcomes by observing crop performance and soil response.

Crops for which relevant

Microbial products can be used in all types of crops, but are particularly relevant for organic farming systems and other low-input cropping systems.

Potential impact

On soil physics

0 +

On soil biology

0 +

On soil chemistry

0 +

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Biomass provision
- Pest and disease regulation

Supporting/cultural:

- Nutrient cycling
- Biodiversity

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

1

Suitable soil

✓	Clay
✓	Sandy
✓	Loamy

Suitable climate

✓	Maritime
✓	Mediterranean
✓	Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

1

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Many suppliers offer microbial biostimulants, but their effectiveness is not always scientifically validated. Farmers should critically assess whether a product delivers results under their specific conditions. Challenges include variable field performance, interactions with native soil microbiota, and regulatory uncertainty under EU law. Integration into broader nutrient and soil health strategies is essential for consistent benefits.

Effective use requires selecting well-adapted microbial strains (e.g. Rhizobium, Mycorrhiza, Azospirillum, Trichoderma) suited to the crop and soil. Application methods must preserve microbial viability, protecting them from UV light and desiccation. Timing, compatibility with inputs, and local soil competition should also be considered.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water**
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms**
- Closing farm nutrient cycles**
- Improving functional soil biodiversity**
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Research on microbial biostimulants has primarily focused on their effects on nutrient uptake, stress tolerance, crop health, and yield. However, knowledge gaps remain regarding their specific modes of action, long-term effects, and optimal application strategies across different crops, soil types, and environmental conditions. Further research is also needed to assess cost-effectiveness and ensure consistent results in field settings.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Left: microbiological ferment treatment on beans. Image © Van Hall Larenstein

Right, source: Backer et al. 2018. Plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (...). *Frontiers in Plant Science* 9: 1473.

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Authors: Jesús Rodrigo-Comino and Lucía Moreno-Cuenca, Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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19. Application of humic products

Basic description of the practice

Humic acid and humate products are negatively charged molecules formed during the decomposition of organic matter. They are typically extracted from organic deposits such as Leonardite or compost. These products are believed to improve soil health and crop growth by enhancing nutrient availability through chelation, stimulating root development, increasing water retention, and supporting microbial activity. Application methods include soil and foliar spraying or seed treatment, depending on the product and intended effect.

Implementation

1. Assess soil and crop needs by identifying specific goals such as improving nutrient uptake, root growth, or water retention.
2. Select humic acid or humate products based on desired outcomes and verified product quality.
3. Determine the correct dosage by following the manufacturer's recommendations tailored to your soil type, crop, and application method.
4. Choose the right application method and timing, applying via soil drench, foliar spray, or seed treatment depending on the product form and crop growth stage.
5. Apply with suitable equipment to ensure even distribution and effective incorporation.
6. Monitor and evaluate by observing crop response and soil condition to adjust future applications if needed.

Crops for which relevant

Application is suitable for various crops.

Potential impact	Application considerations				
On soil physics <div style="text-align: center;">0</div>	Application material cost <div style="text-align: center;">●</div>	Suitable soil		Suitable climate	
		✓ Clay	✓ Maritime		
		✓ Sandy	✓ Mediterranean		
		✓ Loamy	✓ Continental		
On soil biology <div style="text-align: center;">+</div>	Application labour cost <div style="text-align: center;">●</div>	Suitable scale of application			
		< 1ha.	1- 10 ha.	10 - 50 ha.	> 50 ha.
On soil chemistry <div style="text-align: center;">+</div>	Effort/knowledge needed <div style="text-align: center;">2</div>	Extent to which well-researched <div style="text-align: center;">2</div>			
Potential Impact on ecosystems services					
Provisioning/regulating:		Supporting/cultural:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Biomass provision ● Climate regulation ● Pollution control 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Nutrient cycling 			
For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:					

Further considerations

The effectiveness of humic substances under field conditions remains uncertain due to limited scientific validation. While many products are available on the market, it is essential to critically assess their actual benefits for your specific farm.

Successful application depends on selecting the right product type (e.g., potassium humate) tailored to soil and crop requirements, ensuring product quality, and applying it at the appropriate crop growth stage. The response to humic substances varies with soil characteristics such as pH, texture, and organic matter content. Key challenges include inconsistent field performance, a lack of standardized efficacy data, and unclear mechanisms of action across diverse soil and climate conditions.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water**
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity**
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Although positive effects on yields, nutrient use efficiency, and stress tolerance have been demonstrated, review studies highlight several important research gaps that still need to be addressed. There is a need for more field studies to verify the plant growth benefits of humic products across diverse conditions. Scientific acceptance is hindered by unclear mechanisms of action, especially in practical settings. Moreover, product reliability must be enhanced through standardized quality control measures. Lastly, claims of improved soil health lack robust long-term field evidence.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Examples of humic products for agricultural use. The practice sheet does not refer to these products in particular. Images© Wageningen University & Research

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20. Water erosion control by vegetation, mulching or terracing

Basic description of the practice

Soil erosion control measures such as vegetation cover, mulches, and terraces aim to reduce soil loss caused by water. Establishing vegetation involves selecting suitable species and promoting healthy growth, while mulching applies organic or inorganic materials to protect the soil surface. Terraces and stone walls are earth embankments or barriers built to break slope length and slow runoff. Implementation includes land preparation, applying mulch, or earthmoving for terraces. These methods reduce erosion by intercepting raindrops and slowing surface water flow. Vegetation roots help bind the soil, mulches protect and retain moisture, and terraces trap sediment. The overall effect is decreased soil loss, improved water infiltration, and enhanced soil fertility.

Implementation

1. Conduct a soil and topography assessment to understand erosion risk areas and severity on your parcel.
2. Evaluate the cause and context of the water erosion based on this assessment.
3. Determine which measure(s) to apply; consider combining multiple measures for more effective erosion control, as other suitable options may exist beyond those listed here.
4. Implement the measure(s) with proper timing, ideally before the rainy season, for example, seeding cover crops, spreading mulch, or building terraces.
5. Evaluate its effectiveness through visual inspection of water erosion, and adjust the approach or design of the measure if needed.
6. Maintain and repair erosion control structures and vegetation regularly to sustain their benefits over time.

Crops for which relevant

Measures against water erosion are especially important for crops that leave large areas of bare soil and do not provide soil cover during the rainy season.

Potential impact

On soil physics

++

On soil biology

+

On soil chemistry

+

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

1 2 3

Suitable soil

✓	Clay
✓	Sandy
✓	Loamy

Suitable climate

✓	Maritime
✓	Mediterranean
✓	Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1 - 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

4

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Water regulation
- Erosion control
- Pollution control

Supporting/cultural:

- Nutrient cycling
- Provision of habitat
- Biodiversity
- Cultural and non-material elements

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Concerns remain about the effectiveness of erosion control measures, which can vary depending on parcel characteristics, soil type, management practices, and rainfall patterns. Key questions include identifying the optimal combination of techniques and understanding their long-term effects on soil health. Trade-offs may arise, such as increased labor and reduced land availability associated with terraces and stone walls. Constraints include costs for materials like mulch and seed, labor requirements, and the need for specialized equipment. Barriers to adoption often stem from limited awareness of effective methods and potential short-term yield reductions. Cost-benefit analyses should weigh these initial expenses against long-term gains from reduced soil loss and improved water management.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- ✓ Addressing erosion and run-off
- ✓ Improving water management
- ✓ Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- ✓ Increasing soil cover

Research

Research on soil erosion control is extensive, examining the effectiveness of techniques such as vegetation cover, mulches, terraces, and stone walls in reducing soil loss. However, further studies are needed to assess the economic viability of these approaches, their long-term impacts, and how to optimally implement them for different types of parcels.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

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Authors: Jesús Rodrigo Comino and Lucía Moreno Cuenca

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21. Wind erosion control by windbreaks

Basic description of the practice

Wind erosion control mainly relies on windbreaks or shelterbelts which are rows of trees or shrubs planted to reduce wind speed and protect topsoil and crops from damage. These barriers intercept the wind, decreasing its velocity and turbulence by creating a wind shadow downwind. This reduction in wind speed limits soil particle detachment and transport, thereby reducing soil loss. Additionally, windbreaks help create a beneficial microclimate that can improve crop growth conditions.

Implementation

1. Select tree or shrub species suited to your local climate and soil conditions.
2. Ensure proper spacing and orientation by planting the windbreak perpendicular to prevailing wind directions.
3. Plant during the cold season, avoiding periods of frost to promote establishment of the tree species.
4. Maintain the windbreak regularly through pruning and weeding to ensure its effectiveness, especially when it is still young.

Crops for which relevant

Windbreaks are especially beneficial for protecting crops that are vulnerable to wind damage.

Potential impact	Application considerations			
On soil physics <div style="text-align: right;">++</div>	Application material cost <div style="text-align: right;">●</div>	Suitable soil		Suitable climate
		✓ Clay	✓ Maritime	
		✓ Sandy	✓ Mediterranean	
		✓ Loamy	✓ Continental	
On soil biology <div style="text-align: center;">0</div>	Application labour cost <div style="text-align: right;">●</div>	Suitable scale of application		
		< 1ha.	1- 10 ha.	10 - 50 ha.
				> 50 ha.
On soil chemistry <div style="text-align: center;">0</div>	Effort/knowledge needed <div style="text-align: center;">2</div>	Extent to which well-researched <div style="text-align: center;">2</div>		
Potential Impact on ecosystems services				
Provisioning/regulating: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Income provision ● Climate regulation ● Erosion control 		Supporting/cultural: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provision of habitat ● Biodiversity ● Cultural and non-material elements 		
For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:				

Further considerations

Planting windbreaks can boost crop yields by reducing wind damage, but it also decreases available cropping area due to the space occupied by trees. The financial impact of reduced crop area is compounded by initial setup costs. Careful species selection is essential, as some trees may harbor pests or diseases that affect crops. When windbreaks border fields, potential competition for water and nutrients with the crop must be considered. Proper spacing and orientation help maximize wind reduction while minimizing shading and interference with machinery access. Effective windbreak management requires balancing benefits to biodiversity and crop protection with potential trade-offs in productivity and maintenance demands.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Research on windbreaks is substantial, focusing on their effectiveness in reducing wind speed, soil erosion, and improving microclimate. More research is needed on integrating windbreaks into different farming systems and assessing their economic viability. Research into other ecosystem services is extensive.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

A network of field windbreaks to protect the soil against wind erosion. Images © Erwin Cole, USDA Natural Resources Conservation Service. Talken from: <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:FieldWindbreaks.JPG>

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22. Low-pressure tyres

Basic description of the practice

Low-pressure tires are widely used in agriculture to prevent soil compaction, especially on heavier or wetter soils common in Northern and Central Europe. This practice involves adjusting tire pressure according to load and soil moisture, often facilitated by central tire inflation systems (CTIS) that enable real-time pressure changes. By increasing the tire's contact area and lowering internal pressure, soil pressure is reduced, helping maintain soil structure, promote healthier root growth, and improve water infiltration.

Implementation

1. Identify when the risk of soil compaction is highest on your farm and which machines are involved.
2. Before purchasing new tires, explore tire options for your tractors and machinery that reduce soil pressure, such as wider tires, larger diameters, or central tire inflation systems.
3. With your low-pressure tyres: adjust tire pressure according to current field conditions and the specific task being performed.
4. Evaluate the economic benefits over time, considering upfront costs alongside improved soil health and crop productivity.

Crops for which relevant

It is more an issue of relevance for soil type than for crops. It is extra relevant for late-harvested crops with heavy harvesting machinery.

Potential impact

On soil physics

++

On soil biology

0

On soil chemistry

0

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Biomass provision
- Water regulation

Supporting/cultural:

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

1

Suitable soil

- ✓ Clay
- ✓ Sandy
- ✓ Loamy

Suitable climate

- ✓ Maritime
- ✓ Mediterranean
- ✓ Continental

Suitable scale of application

10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

2

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Concerns about low-pressure tires include their higher upfront costs, increased road wear due to the larger contact area, and the need for operators to be properly trained to optimize traction without compromising fuel efficiency or tire lifespan. These tires provide enhanced traction that reduces slippage, which in turn lowers fuel consumption during field operations, benefits especially relevant for heavy machinery on sensitive soils. However, it is important to note that low-pressure tires should not be used to access fields when conditions are very wet, as this nevertheless increases the risk of soil damage..

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction**
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management**
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water**
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Current research indicates that low-pressure tyres in agriculture help reduce soil compaction, promote root growth, increase yields, and improve fuel efficiency, offering both agronomic and economic benefits. However, further studies are needed to evaluate their long-term effects across diverse soil types and climates, as well as to assess their broader environmental impacts, to better support widespread adoption.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Left: Damage from maize harvesting with heavy machinery under wet conditions. Low-pressure tyres can help mitigate such damage. Right: A compacted layer in the subsoil that water cannot penetrate. Images © Wageningen University & Research

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Authors: Ciska Nienhuis, Seerp Wigboldus

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23. Deep-rooting crops (biosubsoiling)

Basic description of the practice

This practice involves growing deep-rooting crops to improve soil structure by taking advantage of certain root systems that can benefit both the topsoil and subsoil. In the topsoil, these roots support better structure and nutrient cycling. In the subsoil, they add organic matter and improve water and air movement. Some roots are capable of penetrating compacted soil layers (though not rocky material), forming biopores that loosen the soil. Decomposing roots and rhizodeposits also supply organic carbon, which encourages the activity of earthworms and soil microorganisms—further promoting the formation of biopores and stable aggregates. Dicotyledonous plants are generally more effective than monocotyledonous crops at penetrating compacted layers.

Implementation

1. Diagnose soil compaction. Identify fields with compacted or poorly structured subsoil using tools such as a spade, penetrometer, or field indicators.
2. Choose suitable deep-rooting crops known for their ability to penetrate compacted layers.
3. Adapt your tillage and rotation plan. Minimize tillage to avoid disturbing root development, and integrate the selected crop into your rotation as a cover or break crop.
4. Sow the deep-rooting crop under favorable conditions. Ensure soil moisture and temperature are adequate for optimal root development.
5. Allow time for root development and monitor effects. Give the crop sufficient time to reach deeper soil layers, and assess changes in soil structure and biological activity over multiple seasons.

Crops for which relevant

"Bio-subsoiler" crops such as lucerne, lupins, chicory, sunflower, sugar beet, carrots, fodder beet, and fodder radish are known for their deep root systems and can be used to alleviate soil compaction.

Potential impact	Application considerations									
On soil physics <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> + ++ </div>	Application material cost <div style="text-align: center;">○</div>	Suitable soil <table border="1"> <tr> <td>✓ Clay</td> <td>✓ Maritime</td> </tr> <tr> <td>✓ Sandy</td> <td>✓ Mediterranean</td> </tr> <tr> <td>✓ Loamy</td> <td>✓ Continental</td> </tr> </table>	✓ Clay	✓ Maritime	✓ Sandy	✓ Mediterranean	✓ Loamy	✓ Continental	Suitable climate	
✓ Clay	✓ Maritime									
✓ Sandy	✓ Mediterranean									
✓ Loamy	✓ Continental									
On soil biology <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> 0 + </div>	Application labour cost <div style="text-align: center;">○</div>	Suitable scale of application <table border="1"> <tr> <td>< 1ha.</td> <td>1- 10 ha.</td> <td>10 - 50 ha.</td> <td>> 50 ha.</td> </tr> </table>			< 1ha.	1- 10 ha.	10 - 50 ha.	> 50 ha.		
< 1ha.	1- 10 ha.	10 - 50 ha.	> 50 ha.							
On soil chemistry <div style="text-align: center;">+</div>	Effort/knowledge needed <div style="text-align: center; background-color: #800000; color: white; padding: 5px;">1</div>	Extent to which well-researched <div style="text-align: center; background-color: #800000; color: white; padding: 5px;">2</div>								
Potential impact on ecosystems services										
Provisioning/regulating: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Biomass provision ● Water regulation ● Erosion control 		Supporting/cultural: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Nutrient cycling 								
For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:										

Further considerations

Implementing biosubsoiling can be challenging and may not be suitable for all farming systems, particularly where adjustments in tillage practices or crop rotations could impact economic returns. The benefits take time to develop as deep-rooted crops often require a full season or more to reach compacted or dry subsoil layers. In shallow or rocky soils the practice may not be feasible. Certain soils may have higher impermeable layers that cannot be penetrated by roots and need machinery.

There are also potential risks. These include re-compaction following mechanical loosening, declines in soil pH in case of legumes and redistribution of nutrients in the soil profile availability. Additionally, certain cover crops may increase the risk of soil-borne diseases. However, with careful selection of crop species, biosubsoiling can provide multiple agronomic and environmental benefits.

Potential soil health benefit

- ✓ Addressing soil compaction
- ✓ Increasing soil organic matter
- ☐ Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- ☐ Addressing erosion and run-off
- ☐ Improving water management
- ✓ Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- ☐ Addressing soil salinisation
- ☐ Addressing soil pollution
- ☐ Suppressing harmful organisms
- ☐ Closing farm nutrient cycles
- ✓ Improving functional soil biodiversity
- ☐ Improving aboveground biodiversity
- ☐ Increasing soil cover

Research

It is well known that soil compaction causes significant yield losses. Many studies evaluating biosubsoiling methods to alleviate this using deep rooting crops have focused primarily on indicators such as crop growth, penetration resistance, and dry bulk density. However, few experiments have provided conclusive evidence that these crops effectively improve subsoil structure or result in clear economic benefits for farmers. Despite this, there is a degree of acceptance and interest among farmers. Important knowledge gaps remain, especially concerning the effects on soil air and water balance.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Rooting patterns of various deep-rooting crops. Image © Joseph Amsili, Jenn Thomas-Murphy, Sandra Wayman, Matt Ryan. Taken from <https://ccemadison.org/events/2023/11/04/postponed-to-online-cover-cropping-for-small-farms-with-salt-city-harvest-farm>

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24. Application of perennial crops

Basic description of the practice

The purpose of integrating perennial crops includes enhancing soil protection and promoting nutrient cycling. Perennial crops are often incorporated into crop rotations by organic and livestock farmers.

It is useful to distinguish between field crops and woody perennials such as shrubs and trees. For example, forage crops like clover, lucerne, and clover-grass mixtures contribute to soil organic matter, and leguminous species also fix nitrogen in the soil. Shrubs and trees can be cultivated in various agroforestry systems, such as surrounding grasslands or planted in strips within arable fields (Practice sheet #3). The roots of perennial legumes and grasses play a key role in improving soil properties, particularly soil structure and density. Deep taproots penetrate the soil profile and help break up plow pans and subsurface compaction. The fibrous root systems of legumes and grasses promote the aggregation of soil particles and form stable aggregates in the seedbed.

Implementation

1. Define objectives such as erosion control, fodder production, carbon sequestration, or diversification
2. Assess crop suitability by evaluating soil type, pH, drainage, and climate conditions to determine appropriate perennial crops
3. Select perennial species that match both your farm objectives and the local growing conditions
4. Plan crop rotation if the perennial is not a shrub or tree
5. Establish and manage the perennial crop using best practices. Management may include grazing, mowing, harvesting, or pruning
6. Monitor and evaluate the impact of the perennial crop on soil structure and nutrient cycling

Crops for which relevant

Examples of perennial crops include lucerne, grassland, grass-clover mixtures and fibrous crops such as miscanthus and bamboo.

Potential impact

On soil physics

+ ++

On soil biology

+ ++

On soil chemistry

+ ++

Application considerations

Application material cost

○ ● ●

Application labour cost

○ ● ●

Effort/knowledge needed

3

Suitable soil

✓	Clay
✓	Sandy
✓	Loamy

Suitable climate

✓	Maritime
✓	Mediterranean
✓	Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

2

Potential Impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Biomass provision
- Climate regulation
- Water regulation
- Erosion control

Supporting/cultural:

- Nutrient cycling
- Provision of habitat
- Biodiversity
- Cultural and non-material elements

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Integrating perennial herbaceous crops into farming systems requires careful planning. These crops often need higher initial investment and may take longer to generate returns than annuals. Success depends on knowledge of crop-specific management, including mowing, grazing, pest control, and nutrient needs. Chosen species must fit existing operations and long-term land use plans. It's important to consider their interactions with soil life, pollinators, and pests, as well as their water needs and drought tolerance. Access to suitable equipment and markets is essential. Good soil preparation and ongoing monitoring help ensure positive impacts on soil health and system performance. The termination of a perennial crop may be more labour-intensive and one needs to take into account the mineralisation of nutrients in the period after. Preferably, choose a crop that is economically beneficial e.g., grass as mow-fertilizer, sandalwood, crops for bio-energy.

Potential soil health benefit

- ✓ Addressing soil compaction
- ✓ Increasing soil organic matter
- ✓ Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- ✓ Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- ✓ Closing farm nutrient cycles
- ✓ Improving functional soil biodiversity
- ✓ Improving aboveground biodiversity
- ✓ Increasing soil cover

Research

Research on perennial crops focuses on their potential to enhance soil structure, ameliorate decompaction, increase carbon sequestration, and increase resilience to climate extremes. Key research gaps involve long-term yield stability and economic viability across diverse European regions.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Lucerne is a perennial forage crop that fixes nitrogen. Image © Victor, N, Vicente Selvas Taken from: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Medicago_sativa_Alfals006.jpg

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25. Soil (phyto) remediation

Basic description of the practice

Phytoremediation is an environmentally friendly, biological technique that uses plants to clean up contaminated soil, water, or air. Certain plant species have the unique ability to absorb harmful substances such as heavy metals, organic pollutants, and excess nutrients through their roots, stems, or leaves. These plants can either store the contaminants in their tissues, break them down into less harmful compounds, or stabilize them to prevent further spread in the environment. Phytoremediation can be applied in various ways, including phytoextraction (removing contaminants by harvesting the plants), phytodegradation (breaking down pollutants through plant metabolism) and phytostabilization (immobilizing contaminants in the soil). This method is cost-effective, sustainable, and often enhances soil health and biodiversity while reducing the need for disruptive mechanical or chemical remediation techniques.

Implementation

1. Analyze your soil to identify specific pollutants through soil testing.
2. Select plant species suited to address the identified contaminants. Consider the type of phytoremediation, as this affects treatment duration and management requirements.
3. Sow the chosen phytoremediation plants and manage them according to best practices.
4. Ensure proper disposal of biomass in accordance with regulations.
5. When the treatment period is complete, conduct follow-up soil tests to assess progress.
6. Terminate the phytoremediation process according to recommended procedures.
7. Resume normal land use if pollution levels have been sufficiently reduced; otherwise, develop a new remediation plan.

Crops for which relevant

This practice may be useful for any contaminated soil where phytoremediation could be effective. Some well-known phytoremediation plants include sunflower, Indian mustard, vetiver grass, alfalfa (lucerne), and ryegrass.

Potential impact

On soil physics

0 + ++

On soil biology

0 + ++

On soil chemistry

0 + ++

Potential Impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

Supporting/cultural:

● Pollution control

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

3

Suitable soil

✓ Clay	✓ Maritime
✓ Sandy	✓ Mediterranean
✓ Loamy	✓ Continental

Suitable climate

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

1

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Applying phytoremediation requires selecting appropriate plant species based on the type, depth, and concentration of soil contaminants such as cadmium, lead, or hydrocarbons. Soil testing is essential to assess contamination levels and guide plant choice. Site-specific factors like pH, drainage, and climate also influence success. Hyperaccumulator plants such as *Brassica juncea* for heavy metals or *Populus* species for organic pollutants should be chosen according to their suitability for local conditions. Challenges include slow rates of remediation and limited effectiveness for mixed or deeply buried contaminants.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- ✓ Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- ✓ Addressing soil salinisation
- ✓ Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

There are a lot of things not researched yet, in particular for sandy and peat soils. In contrast, phytoremediation of saline soils (sodicity) has been extensively studied, particularly following the reclamation of sea clay polders. In river clay soils, the potential of phytoremediation to reduce heavy metal contamination has been explored to some extent but has seen limited practical application.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Barley is known to extract salt from soils. Image © Raul.du-pagne. Taken from: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Escourgeon-Hordeum_vulgare_subsp._vulgare.jpg

Sunflower is known to extract arsenic from soils. Image © Bruce Fritz, U.S. Department of Agriculture Taken from: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sunflowers_helianthus_annuus.jpg

Picture of a field experiment (near Taranto, Italy) where a plant assisted bioremediation strategy with the Poplar clone "Monviso" has been applied. The soil was historically multicontaminated by PCB and heavy metals.

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Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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26. Field inundation

Basic description of the practice

Inundation involves submerging an arable field under water for several months to control soil pathogens, pests and weeds. This practice is an effective alternative to the chemical ways of soil desinfestation. The anaerobic conditions causes fermentation of organic matter which produces toxic conditions to soil organisms. This effectively reduces pathogens but may also have temporary negative effects, such as a decline in beneficial soil biota. Depending on the parcel's condition, soil type, and application method, it can impact soil structure and nutrients both positively and negatively.

Implementation

1. Identify soil pathogens present and assess whether inundation is an effective and economically feasible control measure.
2. Inundation should be carried out at soil temperatures of at least 16 degrees Celcius and for a period of at least 12 weeks.
3. Constructing barriers around the field to keep the water in, closing the drainage pipes and submerging the field to a depth of around 10 cm.
4. Test effectiveness and also soil nutrient levels and pH after inundation.
5. After inundation: add organic material (e.g. compost, organic manure) to restore soil life.

Crops for which relevant

Crop rotations with arable crops that provide a high revenue per hectare.

Potential impact

On soil physics

- 0 +

On soil biology

-

On soil chemistry

- 0 +

Application considerations

Application material cost

●

Application labour cost

●

Effort/knowledge needed

2

Suitable soil

✓ Clay
✓ Sandy
✓ Loamy

Suitable climate

✓ Maritime
✓ Mediterranean
✓ Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

3

Potential Impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

Supporting/cultural:

● Pest and disease regulation

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Inundation is a costly and labor-intensive practice, making it essential to cultivate profitable crops to offset expenses. It is only suitable for flat fields or those that can be easily leveled and requires a reliable water supply. For effective treatment, full inundation must be maintained throughout the entire period of 12 weeks.

Choose a salt-tolerant crop for the next planting such as sugar beet or barley, as inundation may increase soil salinity.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms**
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Considerable research has explored inundation's effectiveness against various pathogens, pests, and diseases, as well as its impact on soil physics, chemistry, and biology. More research on how to restore soil life after inundation is desired. Additionally, information is still lacking on how inundation influences certain pathogens. Furthermore, the effectiveness on heavy clay soil may be lower but this is not entirely clear.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

An inundated fields with the barriers visibly sticking out of the water. Images © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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27. Permanent grassland on poor soils

Basic description of the practice

Establishing permanent grassland means maintaining continuous grass cover without ploughing or reseeding. Instead, the grassland is renovated by overseeding into the existing vegetation. This measure is also (but not only) suitable for fields with poor soil quality that need protection and are not fit for other agricultural uses. Permanent grassland enhances soil carbon sequestration, increases soil organic matter, and stabilizes soil structure, which helps reduce erosion and nutrient runoff. Grasslands with a mix of species, including herbs, further improve ecosystem resilience and soil biological activity. This practice supports long-term soil health by preserving physical structure, reducing the need for fertilizers, and minimizing soil disturbance. It contributes to important ecosystem services such as climate regulation, water retention, and biodiversity.

Implementation

1. Determine which fields are unsuitable for cropping, for example due to poor fertility or erosion risk.
2. Sow a permanent grass mixture, ideally including herbs, with minimal soil disturbance. Autumn is the preferred season for sowing to allow establishment before winter. Spring sowing is also possible.
3. Maintain continuous cover by overseeding when necessary. Avoid tillage and reduce heavy machinery traffic.
4. Monitor and manage: check the grass cover each year, control weeds, and apply organic amendments as needed to support soil health.

Crops for which relevant

Not applicable

Potential impact

On soil physics

+

On soil biology

+

On soil chemistry

+

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

1

Suitable soil

✓ Clay

✓ Sandy

✓ Loamy

Suitable climate

✓ Maritime

✓ Mediterranean

✓ Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha. 1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha. > 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

2

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Water regulation
- Erosion control

Supporting/cultural:

- Provision of habitat

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Grasslands that are in production on soils which have slight slopes, perennial grassland can help protect the soil from compaction, improve water infiltration, and reduce runoff. However, grass yields may decline over time, potentially increasing the need to purchase additional feed. The composition of the grass sward may also change unfavorably, reducing its nutritional value for livestock. As a result, this measure is unlikely to be applied across large areas on most farms, as the economic benefits are generally limited.

Potential soil health benefit

- ✓ Addressing soil compaction
- ✓ Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- ✓ Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- ✓ Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- ✓ Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- ✓ Increasing soil cover

Research

This practice is well-researched, especially regarding its effects on carbon sequestration, erosion control, and biodiversity. Long-term studies confirm benefits for soil structure and organic matter. However, knowledge gaps remain on optimal species mixtures for different soil types and climates, and on economic returns in low-input systems. More research is also needed on integration with livestock management and resilience under extreme weather conditions.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Permanent grassland. Images © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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28. Integrated Crop Management

Basic description of the practice

Integrated Crop Management (ICM) is a systematic approach to applying a diverse set of measures aimed at enhancing the resilience of cropping systems against diseases, pests, and weeds in order to reduce the dependency on pesticides. ICM includes both preventive and direct control strategies, tailored to the crops, soil type, and the farmer's preferences. ICM measures include designing an effective cropping system, such as crop rotation and using field margins, strip cropping, or agroforestry. Selecting resistant and healthy plant varieties is key. A good soil quality and cultivation practices, like planting time, seed rate, and fertilization, also contribute to crop resilience. Monitoring and evaluation help in targeted control, optimizing the choice, timing, and method of control. For direct control, the use of chemical, mechanical, and ecological methods together ensure an efficient approach. Possible benefits for soil quality of ICM depends on the measures implemented and the extent to which pesticide use can be decreased.

Implementation

1. Determine which key pests, diseases, and weeds that are the most problematic on your farm or field.
2. Take time to explore which measures are best suited to your challenges and your farm and crop, e.g., an app, crop rotations, chemical products, tillage etc. In addition, it is possible that there are trade-offs between measures. For example, a measure fitting for weed management might have negative effects on pest management. Choosing (cover) crop varieties with appropriate resistances and/or tolerance is an easy and effective measure to implement.
3. Implement the different measures that you have selected.
4. Monitor the pests, diseases and weeds that are present as prevention should be prioritized over direct control measures. This is especially true for soil-borne pests and diseases, since they require management for a period of (potentially) many years.

Crops for which relevant

ICM is relevant to all crops affected by pests, diseases and weeds but more is known about it for common (cash) crops.

Potential impact	Application considerations				
On soil physics <div style="text-align: center;">0</div>	Application material cost <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="width: 20px; height: 20px; background-color: green; border-radius: 50%;"></div> <div style="width: 20px; height: 20px; border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 50%;"></div> <div style="width: 20px; height: 20px; background-color: orange; border-radius: 50%;"></div> </div>	Suitable soil		Suitable climate	
		✓ Clay	✓ Maritime	✓ Sandy	✓ Mediterranean
		✓ Loamy	✓ Continental		
On soil biology <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="width: 20px; height: 20px; background-color: orange; border-radius: 50%;"></div> <div style="width: 20px; height: 20px; background-color: white; border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 50%;"></div> </div>	Application labour cost <div style="text-align: center;">●</div>	Suitable scale of application			
		< 1ha.	1- 10 ha.	10 - 50 ha.	> 50 ha.
On soil chemistry <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="width: 20px; height: 20px; background-color: orange; border-radius: 50%;"></div> <div style="width: 20px; height: 20px; background-color: white; border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 50%;"></div> </div>	Effort/knowledge needed <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="width: 20px; height: 20px; background-color: white; border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 50%;"></div> <div style="width: 20px; height: 20px; background-color: orange; border-radius: 50%;"></div> </div>	Extent to which well-researched <div style="text-align: center;">2</div>			
Potential Impact on ecosystems services					
Provisioning/regulating:			Supporting/cultural:		
<input type="checkbox"/> Pest and disease regulation			<input type="checkbox"/> Biodiversity		
For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:					

Further considerations

It's important to take the time to assess which practices are most suitable for a specific farm. While the additional labor requirements of integrated crop management (ICM) may be balanced out by reduced pesticide use, the impact may vary significantly depending on the specific measure implemented. To manage expectations; not all pests, diseases, and weeds can effectively be controlled using an ICM strategy, as the necessary knowledge is still evolving. Furthermore, some effects of ICM take time to become apparent, so it's essential to consider both the costs and labor involved.

<https://www.wur.nl/en/research-results/dossiers/file/integrated-crop-management-icm.htr>

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

A significant amount of research on integrated crop management (ICM) exists, but it tends to focus on specific crops and contexts, leading to a variety of practices with differing effectiveness. While the evidence base is strong in certain areas, gaps remain, especially regarding the broader applicability of these practices across diverse farming systems. Long-term studies and research on environmental variability are also lacking. More work is needed to translate science into practice.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Left: Mechanical weed control may be a part of an ICM strategy that reduces the needs for pesticides. Right: Promoting natural enemies for pest control can be part of an ICM strategy. Images © Wageningen University & Research

Date: June 2025

Authors: Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

29. Application of irrigation systems

Basic description of the practice

Irrigation practices aim to optimize water use in agriculture, especially in areas with scarce or irregular rainfall, such as Mediterranean climates. Various systems help improve water efficiency and crop productivity. Drip irrigation delivers water directly to the root zone, reducing evaporation and runoff. Subsurface drip irrigation places water below the soil surface, further limiting losses and enhancing nutrient uptake. Reel irrigation, a type of sprinkler system, is well-suited for larger fields and offers flexible coverage. Controlled drainage manages water table levels with adjustable structures, helping to reduce nutrient leaching and conserve water. Choosing and managing the right system secure yields, conserves resources, and supports environmental protection, making irrigation essential for sustainable farming in water-limited regions.

Implementation

1. Assess site conditions: Evaluate crop water needs, soil type, terrain, and local climate to select the most appropriate irrigation system—such as drip, subsurface drip (SDI), reel irrigation, or controlled drainage.
2. Design and install effectively: Plan an efficient system layout with proper filtration and pressure control. Avoid compacted areas or steep slopes that may hinder even water distribution.
3. Monitor and maintain: Regularly check for clogs, leaks, or uneven coverage. Use soil moisture monitoring to fine-tune irrigation schedules and prevent both under- and over-irrigation.
4. Optimize water and nutrient use: Adjust timing and volume to match crop demand and reduce nutrient leaching. Consider fertigation to deliver nutrients efficiently alongside water.

Crops for which relevant

This practice is for every crop that has water shortage.

Potential impact	Application considerations			
On soil physics 0	Application material cost ●	Suitable soil		Suitable climate
On soil biology 0	Application labour cost ●	✓ Clay	✓ Maritime	✓ Mediterranean
On soil chemistry 0 +	Effort/knowledge needed 2	✓ Sandy	✓ Loamy	✓ Continental
Potential impact on ecosystems services		Suitable scale of application		
Provisioning/regulating: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Biomass provision ● Water regulation ● Erosion control 	Supporting/cultural:	< 1ha.	1- 10 ha.	10 - 50 ha.
		Extent to which well-researched		
		2		
		For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:		

Further considerations

High installation and maintenance costs can be a barrier. A thorough cost-benefit analysis is essential to assess the sustainability and viability of these practices. Other considerations are water supply (amount) and the quality of the water.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- ✓ Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- ✓ Improving water management
- ✓ Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- ✓ Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Further studies are needed to evaluate long-term effects on soil health and the economic viability of these systems across diverse farming contexts. Next step would be integration of irrigation systems in soil health decision support tools.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Left: Reel irrigation over a potato field.
Right: Drip-irrigation in a potato field.

Irrigation in Mediterranean context. Image © Jesús Rodrigo Comino

Date: June 2025
Authors: Jesús Rodrigo Comino, Lucía Moreno Cuenca, Ciska Nienhuis & Seerp Wigboldus
Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

30. Creating water catchments infrastructure

Basic description of the practice

Water catchment infrastructure consists of physical structures such as small dams, stone or earthen walls, and terraces designed to retain, redirect, or slow water flow, especially in sloped or erosion-prone areas. These systems capture rainwater and runoff, reducing erosion, enhancing infiltration, and increasing soil moisture availability. Terracing, in particular, transforms steep slopes into level steps, decreasing runoff velocity and hydrological connectivity. Proper design and regular maintenance are essential to prevent terrace collapse, wall failure, or waterlogging. When well implemented, these structures support soil conservation, reduce sediment loss, and stabilize the landscape. Conversely, neglect or poor construction can lead to landslides, piping, and long-term land degradation. This practice is especially effective in Mediterranean and mountainous regions where water scarcity and slope instability are common, contributing to sustained productivity and ecosystem resilience.

Implementation

1. Select sloped or erosion-prone fields where runoff is high and water retention can improve crop growth and soil stability.
2. Design terraces, small dams, or stone and earthen walls to suit the slope, soil type, and rainfall patterns, considering water flow direction and safe outlets.
3. Use appropriate materials and construction techniques to ensure structural stability, involving trained personnel or community support when possible.
4. Prevent waterlogging and damage by incorporating safe spillways and effective drainage pathways.
5. Perform regular maintenance to inspect and repair any damage, clear debris, and ensure continued effectiveness of the structures.

Crops for which relevant

This practice is particularly relevant for tree crops (e.g. olives, almonds), vineyards, cereals, and vegetables grown on sloped or erosion-prone terrain.

Potential impact

On soil physics

++

On soil biology

+

On soil chemistry

+

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

2

Suitable soil

Clay

Sandy

Loamy

Suitable climate

Maritime

Mediterranean

Continental

Suitable scale of application

1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

3

Potential Impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Biomass provision
- Water regulation
- Erosion control

Supporting/cultural:

- Cultural and non-material elements

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Water catchment infrastructure effectively controls erosion and manages water flow but requires careful design and regular maintenance to prevent failures such as wall collapse or waterlogging. In steep terrain, construction and upkeep can be costly and labor-intensive, posing barriers for smallholder farmers. Improper construction or abandonment may cause long-term degradation, including landslides and increased erosion. On the positive side, well-maintained systems enhance water retention, reduce erosion, and support long-term soil health and productivity. The main trade-offs are the significant initial investment and the ongoing need for maintenance to ensure lasting success.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- ✓ Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- ✓ Addressing erosion and run-off
- ✓ Improving water management
- ✓ Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrients cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- ✓ Improving aboveground biodiversity
- ✓ Increasing soil cover

Research

Research on water catchment infrastructure, including terraces, dams, and walls, is extensive, primarily examining their effectiveness in reducing erosion and improving water retention. However, knowledge gaps remain regarding their long-term environmental impacts, optimal designs for varied landscapes, and economic feasibility for smallholder farmers. Further studies are needed to explore integration with other agricultural practices and to assess their sustainability under changing climate conditions.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Images © Jesús Rodrigo Comino

Date: June 2025

Authors: Jesús Rodrigo Comino and Lucía Moreno Cuenca

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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31. Man-made rills

Basic description of the practice

Man-made rills are shallow channels created by human activities, such as wheel tracks and footpaths, especially on steep slopes in cultivated areas with poor soil. These man-made erosion channels, also called agri-spillways, alter land morphology to reduce surface runoff and improve soil moisture retention when properly managed. This practice helps control water flow and enhances infiltration in erosion-prone areas. Effective implementation relies on appropriate soil tillage, regular monitoring of rill formation, and consideration of soil type, slope, and vegetation cover to maintain soil health.

Implementation

1. Identify sloped, erosion-prone areas with compacted tracks or embankments where rill formation can help manage runoff
2. Design shallow, spaced rills along contour lines or natural flow paths, adapted to slope gradient, soil type, and rainfall intensity
3. Use light equipment or manual tools to create stable, shallow channels without exposing subsoil or increasing erosion risk
4. Inspect rills regularly after rainfall and adjust spacing, depth, or orientation if excessive erosion or waterlogging occurs
5. Prevent clogging or erosion by maintaining ground cover with vegetation or mulch

Crops for which relevant

This practice is especially relevant for vineyards, orchards, and other crops grown on sloped terrain prone to erosion, where effective water management is essential for maintaining soil health.

Potential impact

On soil physics

+

On soil biology

+

On soil chemistry

0

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

1

Suitable soil

Clay

Sandy

Loamy

Suitable climate

Maritime

Mediterranean

Continental

Suitable scale of application

1- 10 ha. 10 - 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

3

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Water regulation
- Erosion control

Supporting/cultural:

- Cultural and non-material elements

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Creating anthropic rills can significantly reduce soil erosion and improve water retention, especially on steep slopes. However, challenges include high labor demands and the risk of localized waterlogging if not properly managed. Barriers to adoption often involve lack of awareness and initial setup costs. Although the practice requires more effort upfront, its long-term benefits include reduced erosion, enhanced water infiltration, and potential savings on irrigation. The key trade-off is balancing the labor-intensive nature of the method with its valuable contribution to soil conservation and sustainable farming.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- ✓ Addressing erosion and run-off
- ✓ Improving water management
- ✓ Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- ✓ Improving functional soil biodiversity
- ✓ Improving aboveground biodiversity
- ✓ Increasing soil cover

Research

Research on anthropic rills is limited and mostly focuses on natural rill formation rather than their intentional use for agriculture. There is little empirical data on their design, effectiveness, and environmental impact as water management or soil conservation tools. More research is needed to measure their benefits, optimize design, assess effects on soil and crops, and evaluate their long-term sustainability in farming systems.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Images © Jesús Rodrigo Comino

Date: June 2025

Authors: Jesús Rodrigo Comino and Lucía Moreno Cuenca

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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32. Deep ploughing and allowing natural decompaction processes

Basic description of the practice

Several agricultural practices, such as vehicle traffic, can cause soil compaction. To address this, mechanical methods like ploughing can be used to restore soil structure. Alternatively, less harmful approaches that support biodiversity include natural recovery processes like freeze-thaw cycles and biomechanical recovery through deep-rooting crops.

As indicated below, the implications vary depending on the decompaction method applied. Allowing natural processes to occur leads to different outcomes compared to mechanical interventions such as deep ploughing.

Implementation

1. Perform ploughing mainly in early autumn when the soil is damp. Turn over the soil to loosen compaction, aerate the soil, and stimulate microbial activity. Remove crop residues during this process to prepare the soil for sowing. Be aware that repeated ploughing can disrupt soil structure and harm soil biota over the long term.
2. Allow natural cycles of soil swelling during wet seasons and shrinking during dry periods to gradually reduce compaction. This process depends on the soil being clay-rich and the local climate supporting distinct wet and dry seasons. Note that swelling and shrinking do not occur effectively in sandy soils.
3. Utilize natural freeze-thaw cycles where water in the soil expands and contracts with temperature changes, helping to break up compacted layers. This mechanism depends on climate conditions that produce freezing temperatures and adequate soil moisture at thawing. This process is limited by soil texture (only effective for clay soils) and moisture content and cannot be precisely controlled.

Crops for which relevant

Not any crop in particular.

Potential impact

On soil physics

+

On soil biology

--

+

On soil chemistry

-

+

Application considerations

Application material cost

Application labour cost

Effort/knowledge needed

0

2

Suitable soil

Clay

Sandy

Loamy

Suitable climate

Maritime

Mediterranean

Continental

Suitable scale of application

< 1ha.

1- 10 ha.

10 - 50 ha.

> 50 ha.

Extent to which well-researched

1

4

Potential impact on ecosystems services

Provisioning/regulating:

- Water regulation
- Erosion control

Supporting/cultural:

- Nutrient cycling
- Biodiversity

For information on relevant legislation and regulations, visit:

Further considerations

Deep ploughing (typically deeper than 30–40 cm) is occasionally used in Europe to disrupt compacted subsoil layers and improve root penetration in crops such as maize or sugar beet. However, it should only be applied when compaction is clearly diagnosed, for example, using a penetrometer.

Key concerns include the loss of deep-soil organic carbon, disruption of soil microbial and fungal networks, and an increased risk of erosion, particularly on sloped or light-textured soils. To prevent long-term damage and restore soil structure and biology, deep ploughing must be followed by soil-improving practices such as cover cropping, reduced tillage, application of organic amendments, and minimizing soil traffic.

Potential soil health benefit

- Addressing soil compaction
- Increasing soil organic matter
- Addressing soil nutrient distortions
- Addressing erosion and run-off
- Improving water management
- Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water
- Addressing soil salinisation
- Addressing soil pollution
- Suppressing harmful organisms
- Closing farm nutrient cycles
- Improving functional soil biodiversity
- Improving aboveground biodiversity
- Increasing soil cover

Research

Research on deep ploughing followed by freeze-thaw cycles on clay soils is limited but promising. Deep ploughing breaks up compacted layers and improves root growth, while freeze-thaw cycles naturally loosen soil and enhance structure. Combining both may further improve soil porosity and reduce the need for repeated mechanical intervention. However, more studies are needed to understand long-term impacts on soil health, carbon dynamics, and erosion risks, especially under different climate and moisture conditions.

For further reading material on this and other practices, visit:

Source: #14 Akkerbouw & Vollegrondsgroente, 2008. <https://edepot.wur.nl/8643>

Date: June 2025

Authors: Wafa Guiga

Contact: <https://soilcrates.eu/>

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3 A summary overview of specific soil health benefits in relation to the 35 practices

Practice		Potential Soil Health Benefit												
		Addressing soil compaction	Increasing soil organic matter	Addressing soil nutrient distortions	Addressing erosion and run-off	Improving water management	Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water	Addressing soil salinisation	Addressing soil pollution	Suppressing harmful organisms	Closing farm nutrients cycles	Improving functional soil biodiversity	Improving aboveground biodiversity	Increasing soil cover
1	Reduced or non-inversion tillage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Buffer zone strips	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Agroforestry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Apply diversified crop rotation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
5	Strip cropping	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6a	Cultivation of cover crops for carbon sequestration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6b	Cover crops for biological nitrogen fixation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6c	Cultivation of catch crops to reduce nitrogen leaching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6d	Selection of cover crops in relation to nematode control	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	Intercropping	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	Tagetes patula for nematode control	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9	Species diversification in grassland	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10	Compost	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
11	Bokashi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12	Biochar	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
13	Seaweed products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
14	Digestate	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
15	Applying clay minerals	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
16	Wood ash	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Practice		Potential Soil Health Benefit												
		Addressing soil compaction	Increasing soil organic matter	Addressing soil nutrient distortions	Addressing erosion and run-off	Improving water management	Enhancing soil resilience handling heat, drought, excessive water	Addressing soil salinisation	Addressing soil pollution	Suppressing harmful organisms	Closing farm nutrients cycles	Improving functional soil biodiversity	Improving aboveground biodiversity	Increasing soil cover
17	Gypsum	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
18	Microbial biostimulants	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
19	Humic products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
20	Water erosion control measures	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
21	Wind erosion control by windbreaks	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
22	Low pressure tyres	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
23	Growing deep rooting crops	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
24	Perennial crops	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
25	Soil (phyto) remediation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
26	Field inundation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
27	Permanent grassland on fields of poor soil quality	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
28	Integrated Crop Management	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
29	Irrigation systems	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
30	Water catchments infrastructure	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
31	Anthropic rills	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
32	Deep ploughing and natural processes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4 A summary overview of ecosystem services in relation to the 35 practices

		Ecosystem services									
		Provisioning	Regulating					Cultural	Supporting		
Practice		Biomass provision	Climate regulation	Water regulation	Erosion control	Pollution control	Pest and disease regulation	Cultural	Nutrient cycling	Provision of habitat	Biodiversity
1	Reduced or non-inversion tillage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2	Buffer zone strips	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3	Agroforestry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Apply diversified crop rotation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
5	Strip cropping	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6a	Cultivation of cover crops for carbon sequestration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6b	Cover crops for biological nitrogen fixation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
6c	Cultivation of catch crops to reduce nitrogen leaching	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
6d	Selection of cover crops in relation to nematode control	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7	Intercropping	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	Tagetes patula for nematode control	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9	Species diversification in grassland	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
10	Compost	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
11	Bokashi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
12	Biochar	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
13	Seaweed products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
14	Digestate	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

		Ecosystem services									
		Provisioning	Regulating					Cultural	Supporting		
Practice		Biomass provision	Climate regulation	Water regulation	Erosion control	Pollution control	Pest and disease regulation	Cultural	Nutrient cycling	Provision of habitat	Biodiversity
15	Applying clay minerals	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
16	Wood ash	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
17	Gypsum	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
18	Microbial biostimulants	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
19	Humic products	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
20	Water erosion control measures	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
21	Wind erosion control by windbreaks	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
22	Low pressure tyres	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
23	Growing deep rooting crops	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
24	Perennial crops	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
25	Soil (phyto) remediation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
26	Field inundation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
27	Permanent grassland on fields of poor soil quality	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
28	Integrated Crop Management	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
29	Irrigation systems	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
30	Water catchments infrastructure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
31	Anthropic rills	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
32	Deep ploughing and natural processes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5 Out-of-the-box inspiration on innovative practices

The following are a few ideas that indicate some of the broader practices that various farmers and research institutes are experimenting with.

Name/ key indication of practice :	Vertical mulching : deepening of the topsoil, adding material to the subsoil
Brief description of what it is about and how it is implemented:	Vertical mulching involves drilling narrow holes into the soil and filling them with compost or other organic materials. This technique mimics natural soil processes, such as those created by earthworms, and is typically applied using hand tools or specialized equipment in compacted or poorly structured soils.
Target/goal – what is it meant to be good for:	The goal is to break up compacted or restrictive layers, restore root growth and water infiltration, and stimulate biological activity in deeper soil zones. By targeting the subsoil directly, this practice supports long-term improvements in soil structure, health, and plant resilience.
Any additional important/useful considerations :	Choose compatible crop species to avoid competition. Ensure sufficient light and moisture for germination. Use precise sowing equipment for good seed-soil contact. Terminate the cover crop at the right moment to avoid yield loss.
Weblink (if available):	
Country where this is practiced already (even if just one/two persons):	Netherlands
Author :	Ciska Nienhuis, WR

Name/ key indication of practice :	Undersowing or direct seeding (i.e. sowing a crop into, for example, a green manure crop)
Brief description of what it is about and how it is implemented:	This practice involves sowing a main crop into a living cover crop (direct seeding) or establishing a second crop beneath an existing one (undersowing), typically without tillage. It requires careful timing and adapted sowing equipment to ensure good seed placement while limiting competition between plant species.
Target/goal – what is it meant to be good for:	The goal is to maintain continuous soil cover to protect and regenerate soil health. This includes reducing erosion, suppressing weeds, stimulating biological activity, and improving resilience to drought and extreme weather, while promoting efficient nutrient cycling.
Any additional important/useful considerations :	Timing and crop choice are critical to avoid competition for light, water, and nutrients between the cover crop and the main crop. In some systems, terminating the cover crop mechanically or through frost is necessary to avoid interference with the cash crop.
Weblink (if available):	https://www.kairos-agrifood.com/loonwerk-directzaai
Country where this is practiced already (even	Netherlands and Canada

if just one/two persons):	
Author:	Ciska Nienhuis, WR

Name/ key indication of practice :	Aerating slurry
Brief description of what it is about and how it is implemented:	Slurry aeration involves adding oxygen to manure before application, either during storage or shortly before spreading. This process shifts decomposition from anaerobic to aerobic, making the slurry more stable and biologically compatible with soil ecosystems. The technique is used in both livestock and mixed farming systems and can be done intermittently or continuously, depending on equipment and management
Target/goal – what is it meant to be good for:	The main goal is to reduce the presence of harmful anaerobic compounds, improve the nutrient profile of the slurry, and enhance its effect on soil life. Aerated slurry can contribute to reduced methane and odour emissions and support soil health—provided it is applied under the right conditions to avoid increased ammonia or nitrous oxide losses.
Any additional important/useful considerations:	Avoid over-aeration, as it can raise pH and increase ammonia losses. Apply aerated slurry quickly after treatment, ideally via injection or incorporation. Monitor temperature and foaming, and consider combining with acidification or cover systems to minimize emissions.
Weblink (if available):	
Country where this is practiced already (even if just one/two persons):	Netherlands
Author:	Ciska Nienhuis, WR

Name/ key indication of practice :	Hedges
Brief description of what it is about and how it is implemented:	Hedges are impermeable rows of shrubs and trees along field margins. Besides their functional goal they are host to all sorts of belowground and aboveground biodiversity. And serve all sort of ecosystem functions.
Target/goal – what is it meant to be good for:	Similar to field margins, but higher C uptake, targeting different insects and birds, reduce erosion,
Any additional important/useful considerations:	could be hot spots/buffer zones for soil fungi (saprotrophs and AMF)
Weblink (if available):	https://www.naturetoday.com/intl/nl/nature-reports/message/?msg=29235
Country where this is practiced already (even if just one/two persons):	NL, EN, FR, ...
Author:	Sigrid Dassen, VHL

6 Relevant policies and regulations for the following countries: Spain, France, Italy, Ireland, and the Netherlands

The QR-code in the practice sheets on policies and regulations links to a page on the SOILCRATES websites which hosts an initial draft document which outlines relevant policies and regulations for soil health practices as described in this catalogue (<https://soilcrates.eu/resources/relevant-policies-and-regulations/>). Descriptions pertain to the situation in Spain, France, Italy, Ireland, and the Netherlands, and includes a comparison of related conditions in these countries. It is still a draft document, and it will be adapted by SOILCRATES partners over the next few years.

7 Further reading – overview of sources in relation to the practices

The following references to further reading can also be accessed through the QR-code on the practice sheets. It links to a location on the SOILCRATES website, which will be kept updated as work in SOILCRATES progresses (<https://soilcrates.eu/resources/further-reading-on-soil-improvement-practices/>).

7.1 Overview table

Information Sources:	Practices																																
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7.2 The listed practices

Identification number of the practice	Practice short description	Brief explanation if it is not obvious
(Soil) cultivation (system) related		
1	Apply minimum tillage or no-tillage	(significantly) Reduced soil disturbance
2	Apply buffer strips (also see riparian buffer zones)	A buffer strip is an area of land maintained in permanent vegetation that helps to control air quality, soil quality, and water quality, etc.
3	Apply agroforestry system	
	Food forest	can be in combination with land retirement
	Silvopastoral	
	Sylvicultural	
	Agrisilvopastoral	
	Riparian buffer zones	
Choice of crops/ cropping system /crop diversification related		
4	Apply diversified crop rotation	
5	Apply strip cropping	
6	Apply cover crops (variety of options)	split up in four types to describe them in relation to the specific purpose
7	Inter-cropping	
8	Apply Tagetes (Marigold)	
9	Species diversification in grassland	
Organic amendments		
10	Apply green compost, vermicompost, termophilic compost, compost tea	
11	Apply bokashi	
12	Apply biochar	
13	Apply seaweed	
14	Apply digestate	
Inorganic amendments		
15	Apply vermiculite, lava split, bentonite, clinoptilolite, and other clay minerals/rocky material	Rock powders and other natural mineral products with multiple trace elements.
16	Apply ashes	
17	Apply gypsum	

Identification number of the practice	Practice short description	Brief explanation if it is not obvious
Soil stimulants		
18	Apply microbial biostimulants	Compost teas, Effective Micro-organisms, Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS), Biodynamic preparations, and other microbial inoculants or biostimulants applied to soil, manure, seeds, root balls, or foliage.
19	Apply humic acids and humate products (e.g. perlhumus), sea weed	Non-microbial biostimulants
Counteract physical conditions		
20	Apply water erosion/runoff control, e.g. through contouring	
21	Apply wind erosion control field windbreaks and shelterbelts (also see agroforestry)	
22	Apply low pressure tyres on tractor	Prevent/undo compaction
23	Apply deep rooting crops	Prevent/undo compaction
24	Apply perennial crops	
Soil repair		
25	Apply soil remediation; phytoremediation	Clean soil from contaminants
26	Apply inundation	
Preventative measures		
27	Apply permanent ground cover	
28	Apply system of minimal use of pesticides; e.g. through mechanical weed control, biological control of pests, etc.	
Water management		
29	Irrigation	Reel irrigation, drip irrigation, subirrigation, and controlled drainage optimize water management
30	Water catchments infrastructure	Deposits and dams, walls to direct water, terracing
31	Anthropic rills	
Soilcompaction (additional)		
32	Deep ploughing	

7.3 The listed sources

Identification number	Source
<i>EU level and international sources</i>	
1	Practice sheets which probably will not be ready in time to draw on: https://inbestsoil.eu/resources/
2	Best4Soil project outputs: https://www.best4soil.eu/factsheets/ ; https://www.best4soil.eu/videos
3	Techniques for the recovery of compacted soils in Europe: https://edepot.wur.nl/629799
4	Building soils for better crops: https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/sites/default/files/2022-10/BSBC%20Excerpt%2001.%20Start%2C%20End%2C%20Core%20Messages%20%2831%20pages%29_0.pdf
5	Ontario best practices soil health: https://bmpbooks.com/resource/soils/
6	Farming with soil life: https://www.sare.org/wp-content/uploads/Farming-with-Soil-Life.pdf
7	Soil management on organic farms: https://www.organic-crop-production.com/organic_crop_production/soil_management_organic_farms/management_practices_soil_health.htm
8	Innovative soil management practices across Europe: https://shinyapp.cra.wallonie.be/isompe-inventory/
9	Sustainable agricultural practices and methods - European Commission
10	U.S. department of Agriculture: 4 main principles to improve soil health: https://www.farmers.gov/conservation/soil-health
11	https://www.diverimpacts.net/de/service/practice-abstracts.html
<i>Source from the Netherlands</i>	
1	Sustainable soil management: https://publications.deltares.nl/1230934c.pdf
2	Practices for soil carbon sequestration: https://slimlandgebruik.nl/sites/default/files/2023-07/Brochure_maatregelen-voor-het-vastleggen-van-koolstof-minerale-bodems.pdf ; CO2Bodem Klei Slim Landgebruik; CO2Bodem Zand Slim Landgebruik
3	Practices for sustainable soil management: https://research.wur.nl/en/publications/overzicht-maatregelen-duurzaam-bodembeheer
4	Practice factsheets PPS Better Soil Management: https://www.beterbodembeheer.nl/nieuws/prestaties-van-bodemmaatregelen-overzichtelijk-voor-de-praktijk/
5	Agricultural water management and practices: https://agrarischwaterbeheer.nl/thema/bodembeheer/ ; Maatregelen - Deltaplan Agrarisch Waterbeheer
6	Good soil management: https://www.goedbodembeheer.nl/Maatregelen
7	Key performance indicators for sustainable agriculture: https://wiki.groenkennisnet.nl/space/kpikll
8	https://www.waterschaplimburg.nl/publish/pages/5037/water_vasthouden_op_land_bouwpercelen_in_zuid-limburg_15_maatregelen_def.pdf
9	https://www.best4soil.eu/assets/factsheets/nl/23.pdf
10	https://agrarischwaterbeheer.nl/maatregelen/daw_overzicht_maatregelen_bootlijst_september_2022.pdf of
11	Factsheets Louis Bolk Instituut – example: https://www.louisbolk.nl/sites/default/files/publication/pdf/factsheet-toepassing-van-vaste-organische-mest.pdf

Identification number	Source
12	https://edepot.wur.nl/161084
13	https://www.louisbolck.nl/thema/duurzaam-bodembeheer
14	https://www.aaltjesschema.nl/Maatregelen/Biologischegrondontsmetting/Inundatie.aspx
15	https://www.louisbolck.nl/sites/default/files/publication/pdf/agroforestry-op-het-landbouwbedrijf.pdf
16	https://groenkennisnet.nl
17	https://www.handboekbodemenbemesting.nl/nl/handboekbodemenbemesting/ingen/bodem.htm
18	Bouwvoorverbetering door middel van diepe grondbewerking - https://edepot.wur.nl/8643

Sources from France

- 1 Multiscale assessment of soil ecosystem services in agroecosystems: <https://hal.inrae.fr/hal-03299072/document>
- 2 Good practices in Agroforestry: [https://www.agroforesterie.fr/documentation/Agronomic practices favorable to functional biodiversity implemented by farmers in DEPHY and GIEEs collectives in Nouvelle-Aquitaine:](https://www.agroforesterie.fr/documentation/Agronomic_practices_favorable_to_functional_biodiversity_implemented_by_farmers_in_DEPHY_and_GIEEs_collectives_in_Nouvelle-Aquitaine)
- 3 <https://agroecologie.org/retour-experience>
https://collectifs-agroecologie.fr/fileadmin/user_upload/National/187_eve-CollectifsAgroecologie/Documents/Nouvelle-Aquitaine/2021_Synthese_pratiques_agronomiques_biodiv_fonctionnelle.pdf
- 4 Agroforestry in an organic farming system: <https://www.produire-bio.fr/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/Recueil-agroforesterie-VF.pdf>
- 5 Impact of cover crops: <https://www.adaf26.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Presentation-Couverts-GRAB-17-10-2023-1.pdf>
- 6 https://rd-agri.fr/detail/DOCUMENT/chambres_d'agriculture_306068
- 7 <https://agriculture-de-conservation.com/Le-biochar-enjeu-climatique-potentiel-agronomique-et-leviers-pour-une.html>
https://www.ecovi.fr/blogs/infos/actualite-scientifique-l-utilisation-du-bokashi-dans-l-agriculture-biologique?srsId=AfmBOoCxFkSLY_TSmUVuoZie3jZse7MTBQiAJpIJggfPY1u6OrPN4
- 8 https://ecophytopic.fr/sites/default/files/Agronomie_Fiche3_Cultiver%20sans%20la_bour_MD.pdf
- 9

Sources from Ireland

- 1 <https://www.farmingfornature.ie/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Climate-Actions-Tillage.pdf>
- 2 <https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/publications/2024/Farming-for-a-Better-Future---Johnstown-Castle-July-2024.pdf>
- 3 <https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/publications/2024/Branching-Out.pdf>
- 4 <https://intercropvalues.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/7-Principles-of-design-of-intercropping.pdf>
- 5 <https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/publications/2024/Branching-Out.pdf>
- 6 <https://www.farmersjournal.ie/more/climate-and-environment/biochar-a-growing-sector-in-ireland-760936>
- 7 <https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/publications/2022/Hemp4Soil---Community-Soil-Biodiversity-Project.pdf>
- 8 <https://bim.ie/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/BIM-Technical-Report.pdf>

Identification number	Source
9	https://www.seai.ie/sites/default/files/renewable-energy/bioenergy/biogas-boilers/Anaerobic-Digestion-Implementation-Guide.pdf
10	https://www.tipperarycoco.ie/sites/default/files/2022-07/Code%20of%20Good%20Practice%20Biosolids%20in%20Agriculture-Guidelines%20for%20Farmers.pdf
11	https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/publications/2020/Biostimulant-biofertilisers-and-biopesticides.pdf
12	https://www.fertilizer-assoc.ie/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Fert-Assoc-Tech-Bulletin-No.-2-Lime.pdf
13	https://www.farmingfornature.ie/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/Watercourse-Management-1.pdf
14	https://centerforagroforestry.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/06_Windbreaks_TrainingManual_2024Master_0410_Digital-7.pdf
15	https://agroforestry.net.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/20190529_factsheet_06_en_web.pdf
16	https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/rural-economy/farm-management/chapter6.pdf
17	https://www.hsa.ie/eng/publications_and_forms/publications/agriculture_and_forestry/guidance_on_the_safe_use_of_tractors_and_machinery_on_farms.pdf

Sources from Italy

1	Voluntary guidelines for sustainable soil management: https://openknowledge.fao.org/handle/20.500.14283/i6874it
2	Strategic Plan CAP Italy, 2023: https://www.reterurale.it/downloads/Piano_Strategico_della_PAC_23-27_v.2.1.pdf
3	Ministerial Decree 46/2019 – Annex 4 – 2.1 and 2.3; Regulation relating to reclamation, environmental restoration and emergency, operational and permanent safety interventions of areas intended for agricultural production and livestock farming, pursuant to Article 241 of Legislative Decree 3 April 2006, no. 152. (19G00052); <a "="" href="https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:ministero.ambiente.e.tutela.territorio.e.mare:decreto:2019-03-01;46!vig=">https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:ministero.ambiente.e.tutela.territorio.e.mare:decreto:2019-03-01;46!vig=
4	Guidelines for the preparation of plans monitoring or management of the impact on soil quality and carbon in soil. ISPRA. 2022; https://www.mase.gov.it/sites/default/files/archivio/normativa/linee_guida_ISPRA_implementazione_RED_II.pdf
5	Legislative Decree 75/2010; Amendment and revision of the fertiliser framework, pursuant to article 13 of the law of 7 July 2009, no. 88. (10G0096); https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2010-04-29;75
6	LIFE HELPSOIL. Soils and adaptation to climate change through sustainable farming techniques; https://www.reterurale.it/buonepraticheLIFE/helpsoil
7	Joint Research Centre; Project SoCo information sheets, 2009; https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/projects/soco-fact-sheets
8	Consorzio Italiano Biogas; The agricultural digestate for organic fertilization, 2024; https://www.consorziobiogas.it/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Digestato-Manuale-B5-2024-WEB.pdf
9	Legislative Decree 99/1992 on the implementation of Directive No. 86/278/EEC concerning the protection of the environment, in particular soil, in the use of sewage sludge in agriculture; https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/1992/02/15/092G0139/sg
10	FAO, 2017 (https://openknowledge.fao.org/handle/20.500.14283/i6874it
11	http://www.irri.it/docs/irrigazioneagoccia.pdf

Identification number	Source
12	https://subirrigazione.it/wp-content/uploads/2014/12/manuale-subirrigazione.pdf
13	https://openknowledge.fao.org/handle/20.500.14283/i6874it ; https://aqua.crupa.it/media/documents/Aqua_www/pubblicazioni/Completo%20E514.pdf
14	https://soil4life.eu/wp/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/Soil4Life_B4_Linee-Guida-per-luso-sostenibile-del-Suolo.pdf
15	https://openknowledge.fao.org/items/19e0aa53-a958-4da8-9723-f29c8f90a346
Sources from Spain (Spanish language sources)	
1	Bautista Cruz, A., Etchevers Barra, J., Castillo, R.F. del, Gutiérrez, C., 2004. La calidad del suelo y sus indicadores. Ecosistemas 13, 90–97. http://hdl.handle.net/10045/8708
2	Cerdà, A., 2003. El clima y el hombre como factores de la estabilidad estructural del suelo. Un estudio a lo largo de los gradientes climático-altitudinales. Cuaternario y Geomorfología 12, 3–14. https://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/4599
3	Cobertera, L.E., 1993. Edafología aplicada: suelos, producción agraria, planificación territorial e impactos ambientales. Cátedra, Madrid. https://dama.umh.es/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991000370719706331&context=U&vid=34CVA_UMH:VU1&lang=es
4	FAO, 2000. Manual de prácticas integradas de manejo y conservación de suelos. Roma, Italia. https://books.google.es/books?id=kZCpFvW1EC&printsec=copyright&hl=es#v=onepage&q&f=false
5	Assessment of agri-spillways as a soil erosion protection measure in Mediterranean sloping vineyards https://www.researchgate.net/publication/316475800_Assessment_of_agri-spillways_as_a_soil_erosion_protection_measure_in_Mediterranean_sloping_vineyards
6	Porta, J., López-Acevedo, M., Poch, R., 2014. Edafología: uso y protección de suelos, Tercera. ed. Mundiprensa, Madrid. https://books.google.com.ec/books?id=7x1fAwAAQBAJ&printsec=copyright#v=onepage&q&f=false
7	Quiroga, A., Bono, A., 2008. Manual de fertilidad y evaluación de suelos. INTA. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/380891268_Edicion_2012_Manual_de_fertilidad_y_evaluacion_de_suelos
8	USDA, 1999. Guía para la evaluación de la calidad y salud del suelo. USDA, Departamento de Agricultura, Servicio de Investigación Agrícola, Servicio de Conservación de Recursos Naturales, Instituto de Calidad de Suelos, Lincoln, Nebraska, Estados Unidos. Traducción al español (2000) de Soil Quality Test Kit Guide realizada por Alberto Lutens y Juan Carlos Salazar Lea Plaza (Área de Cartografía de Suelos y Evaluación de Tierras, Instituto de Suelos CRN-CNIA-INTA, Argentina). https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/sites/default/files/2022-10/Gu%C3%ADa%20para%20la%20Evaluaci%C3%B3n%20de%20la%20Calidad%20y%20Salud%20del%20Suelo.pdf
9	Water Use Efficiency of Surface Drip Irrigation versus an Alternative Subsurface Drip Irrigation Method https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)IR.1943-4774.0000745
10	Global synthesis of the classifications, distributions, benefits and issues of terracing https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2016.06.010
11	Terraced landscapes: From an old best practice to a potential hazard for soil degradation due to land abandonment https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ancene.2014.03.002

Identification number	Source
12	Agricultural Terraces Special Issue Preface https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.3129
13	Conceptualization of Water Flow Pathways in Agricultural Terraced Landscapes https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2764
14	Marginal Lands and Erosion in Terraced Fields in the Mediterranean Mountains: A Case Study in the Camero Viejo (Northwestern Iberian System, Spain) https://www.jstor.org/stable/3674134
15	Effects of farming terraces on hydrological and geomorphological processes. A review https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2015.01.021

8 Longlist from which practices were selected

	Practice short description	Brief explanation if it is not obvious
<i>(Soil) cultivation (system) related</i>		
	Apply minimum tillage or no-tillage	(significantly) Reduced soil disturbance
	Apply buffer strips (also see riparian buffer zones)	A buffer strip is an area of land maintained in permanent vegetation that helps to control air quality, soil quality, and water quality, etc.
	Apply residue management	handling of stems, leaves, chaff and husks that remain in the fields after crops are harvested for grain, seed or fiber.
	Apply agroforestry system	
	Food forest	can be in combination with land retirement
	Silvopastoral	
	Sylvicultural	
	Agrisilvopastoral	
	Riparian buffer zones	
	Terrace cultivation	on steep slopes
	Contour tillage	
	Animal tillage	Using pigs/chickens etc to open up the soil
	Apply mulch tillage	
	Mob-grazing / planned grazing	(for pasture farmers)
	Introduce more animal species into system	Different species have different foraging habits; fertilize soils; increase plant and soil microbe diversity. Can make for more resilient systems
	Use traditional breeds of animals	More suited to local environment; less likely to require inputs/medicines which have an impact on soil
<i>Choice of crops/ cropping system /crop diversification related</i>		
	Apply diversified crop rotation	
	Apply strip cropping	
	Apply sod crop in rotation	
	Apply cover crops (variety of options)	split it up in describing them per purpose
	Inter-cropping	
	Mixed cropping	Differs from intercropping. Two or more crops planted and harvested together
	Apply Tagetes (Marigold)	
	Apply break crop	
	Species diversification in grassland	
	Use of legumes (either in rotation, inter-cropped or mixed cropped)	To fix atmospheric nitrogen

	Use seeds saved from locally adapted crops	Improved yield. They will be more suited to the local conditions (soil/climate/etc). We also need more genetic variability within the crops we grow especially as a buffer to climate change. The plant goes hand-in-hand with the soil...
<i>Organic amendments</i>		
	Apply ramial wood chip (RWC)	Increase biological activity (esp fungal), SOC, P availability, water holding capacity, etc
	Fatty acid amendments e.g. fish hydrolysate, neem oil	Feeds mycorrhizal and saprophytic fungi
	Apply clippings (e.g. from side of the road), and all kinds of raw fibres such as coconut, alfalfa, etc.	
	Apply green compost, vermicompost, thermophilic compost, compost tea	
	...+ other composts: black soldier fly larvae (bsfl) compost; Johnson-Su 'BEAM' compost; woody compost	
	Apply fermented plant extracts, e.g. comfrey, nettle, etc	
	Apply liquid biofertiliser	Made from water, cow manure, raw milk, molasses, wood ash; optional additions of yeast, worm castings, kelp extract, rock dust. Anaerobes extract and chelate nutrients. Used as a foliar spray
	Apply mushroom compost	
	Apply bokashi	
	Apply biochar	
	Apply straw	
	Apply bloodmeal, bone meal, fishmeal, etc.	Dead animal products
	Apply pure manure	
	Apply seaweed	
	Apply thick fraction manure; fibre fraction manure	
	Apply manure mixed with fibres	
	Apply digestate	
	Apply mulch (organic)	
	Chop and drop'	Cut plant material and drop on ground. Serves as a compost and a mulch. Often used in mixed-cropping systems, e.g. agroforestry.
	Apply effective microorganisms (EMs)	Facultative microbes (can live in both aerobic and anaerobic conditions) can be cultivated in a passive brewing process: e.g. lactic acid bacteria (LAB)
	Apply Indigenous Microorganisms (IMOs) and associated preparations	Used to increase soil biology. Collect IMOs from local area using rice/wheat bran, etc.
	Mycorrhizal inoculants	
<i>Inorganic amendments</i>		

Apply vermiculite, lava split, bentonite, clinoptilolite, and other clay minerals/rocky material	Rock powders and other natural mineral products with multiple trace elements.
Apply sludge	Struvite?
Apply lime, shells	Raising the pH
Apply gravel, sand	
Apply ashes	
Apply pH lowering chemical additives	
Apply gypsum	
<i>Soil stimulants</i>	
Apply trace elements	Manganese, molybdeen, etc.
Apply microbial biostimulants	Compost teas, Effective Micro-organisms, Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS), Biodynamic preparations, and other microbial inoculants or biostimulants applied to soil, manure, seeds, root balls, or foliage.
Apply humic acids and humate products (e.g. perhumus), sea weed	Non-microbial biostimulants
Apply product for improving nutrient availability	Hormons, etc.
Apply system of high calcium limestone, gypsum, and other minerals applied to achieve specific ratios of cations (Ca, Mg, K, Na) or other nutrient claimed to improve soil and crop health.	Albrechts method? So this is about a particular system of application, not just the products by themselves.
<i>Counteract physical conditions</i>	
Apply water erosion/run-off control, e.g. through contouring	
Apply wind erosion control field windbreaks and shelterbelts (also see agroforestry)	
Apply drainage system	
Apply (deep) ploughing, spading	Prevent/undo compaction
Apply low pressure tyres on tractor	Prevent/undo compaction
Use wider tyres on machinery	
Use lighter machinery (e.g. two-wheeled tractor for smaller farming operations)	reduce compaction
Apply practice/habit of only entering field when dry enough	Prevent/undo compaction
Apply deep rooting crops	Prevent/undo compaction
Apply perennial crops	
(Land retirement)	
Apply fallow	
Path management (for small farms/market gardens)	e.g. woodchip; stropharia inoculated woodchip; living pathways, etc
<i>Soil repair</i>	
Apply soil remediation; phytoremediation	Clean soil from contaminants
Apply inundation	

	Apply subsurface drainage	Apply and optimize existing drainage infrastructure and Maintain functional drainage system
<i>Preventative measures</i>		
	Apply permanent ground cover	
	Apply system of minimal use of pesticides; e.g. through mechanical weed control, biological control of pests, etc.	
	Anaerobic soil disinfection	
	Biosolarization	
	Shelterbelts	reduce wind stress (and thus reduce evapotranspiration) and damage / increases pest control (e.g. by providing habitat for beetles, etc), ++
	No-till	Minimise damage to soil biology and soil structure
<i>Watermanagement</i>		
	Irrigation	Reel irrigation, drip irrigation, subirrigation, and controlled drainage optimize water management
	Water storage	Underground and basins
	Water catchments infrastructure	deposits and dams
	Use of soil moisture sensors	
	measurement crop water needs	
	deficit irrigation	
	use of acceptable water quality	

9 Conclusion

This catalogue provides a first set of inspirational outlines of selected soil health improvement practices. They are limited to descriptions of essentials about the practices. By providing a 'quick overview', readers may select the ones they are particularly interested in and then explore more details in the recommended reading materials.

The catalogue is meant to help jumpstart the SOILCRATES living labs by providing a background for discussion and considering together as living lab participants what specific experiments would be of particular relevance and use to participating farmers.

This catalogue should be considered as an intermediate product of SOILCRATES and other tasks, notably T5.4, will build on this initial overview and develop it further, including translation into different languages.

